

The Fall of Adam and the Depths of Primal Repression

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Part I

The Latent Content of the Fall Narrative

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Abstract

Although the biblical narrative of the Fall of Man imbued the imagination of countless societies more profoundly than the Greek myth of Oedipus – etching a decisive mark upon Greece itself, evident in its conversion from paganism to Christianity – Sigmund Freud posited the Oedipal complex as the root of humanity’s “knowledge of good and evil”, without ever directly engaging the Fall narrative. To unearth deeper insights on the nature of sin, I brought Adam upon the couch of Freudian psychoanalysis. This inquiry uncovered a pre-Oedipal sense of guilt at least as grave as that of Oedipus: guilt towards the mother, arising from birth itself, intimately bound to the fear of death, and nourishing the Oedipal guilt. The “Fall of Man” is the fall of an “apple” from the womb. This finding is of import for psychoanalysis, education, theology and obstetrics.

Keywords

Book of Genesis, Adam, Eve, original sin, death, birth, matricide, umbilicus, breathing, primal repression, natural theology, air

Introduction

The narrative of *The Fall of Man* (Moses, uncertain date, pp. 15-16) has long been viewed as a foundational story of human guilt. Despite its profound cultural impact and ubiquity (Johnson, 2008, p. 9), this narrative has been largely overlooked in psychoanalytic theory. Freud, in particular, focused on the Oedipus complex, modelled on the Greek myth of the Theban parricide (Homer, circa 700 BCE, p. 233; Sophocles, ca. 430 BCE), to explain the primal guilt (Freud, 1913, pp. 153-154) and moral development in humans. This emphasis on Oedipus had occluded the possibility of a more fundamental source of the sense of guilt, most strikingly evidenced by children who, notwithstanding the absence or minimal presence of a father, exhibit pronounced compunction – a phenomenon that has long lain neglected within psychoanalytic theory. In this paper, I aim to address this gap by applying Freudian psychoanalysis to the Fall of Adam and Eve.

To be exact, my original aim in analysing the narrative of the Fall was not to explore potential pre-Oedipal origins of guilt. In

truth, my reflections began when, while reading page 4 of *An Outline of Psycho-Analysis* (Freud, 1938), I asked myself what the very first stimulant of our erogenous zones was. Far from thinking, as Freud did, of breastfeeding, it occurred to me that the very first “sexual” stimulant was not maternal milk, but rather amniotic fluid, and I associated this intuition with the Fall, which likewise touches upon the origin of sexual stimulation. I thus formed the idea that this narrative is related to intrauterine life.

Curiously, Freud never thought to invoke the narrative of the Fall in order to persuade those who, while agreeing with Augustine of Hippo’s claim (ca. 411 CE, p. 272) that “lust is natural, since every man is born with it”, nonetheless denied that “a child comes into the world with its sexual instincts and activities” (Freud, 1909, p. 42, slightly modified for conciseness). My idea that infantile “sexuality” begins in the womb aligns perfectly with the Augustinian doctrine of the congenital nature of sin. However, it was still not to uncover pre-Oedipal connections between sexual desire and guilt that I decided to delve further into the analysis of the narrative of the Fall. In fact, what motivated me was the desire

to discover what Freud called the “primal repression” (Freud, 1915, pp. 148 and 180-181), a repression that I naturally associated with the amniotic origin of desire that I had just perceived.

What was the point of going further in the analysis of the biblical narrative to find the content of the primal repressed? Would it not have sufficed to declare that our first repressed is the desire to immerse our lips in the amniotic fluid? Either because I needed to find more arguments in the narrative of the Fall to support this hypothesis; or because, unconsciously, I knew that the first repressed could not be reduced to the desire to drink a warm liquid barely different from ordinary water; or perhaps because I could not see how it would be “guilty” to drink this liquid, I launched into the analysis of the sacred story, at once impelled by the etymological kinship between the French words *originnaire* and *originel* – as in *refoulement originnaire* (“primal repression”) and *péché originel* (“original sin”) – which promised to unveil, in a single stroke, both the genesis of desire and that of guilt.

Through this analysis, I uncovered a pre-Oedipal sense of guilt intricately bound to the mother and to the fear of death – a foundational stratum that both precedes and informs the more familiar Oedipal complex.

In this essay, I trace the maternal source of bad conscience, drawing upon insights from literature and philosophy to substantiate my findings. This discovery may profoundly impact theology, psychoanalysis, education and obstetric practices that could prevent an excessive sense of culpability.

Materials and Methods

The primary material for this study is the biblical account of the Fall of Adam and Eve as narrated in the third chapter of Genesis. The method employed is a psychoanalytic interpretation of the symbolic elements of the narrative. Approached as a psychological product that reflects deep-seated unconscious processes shared across individuals, the sacred text is examined within the framework of Freudian psychoanalysis, with a focus on the dynamics of guilt. No clinical case material or other form of

empirical data was employed; the analysis remains theoretical, grounded in psychoanalytic literature and religious scripture.

In the discussion section, I extend my analysis by aligning the narrative of the Fall with the myth of the Androgyne (Plato, ca. 360 BCE, pp. 559–563), drawing on other literary and philosophical works – Friedrich Nietzsche’s *On the Genealogy of Morals* (1887) in particular – to reinforce my conclusions.

This methodology exemplifies the integration of psychoanalytic theory with religious and cultural texts, allowing to reveal new layers of meaning and contribute to a deeper understanding of the origins of the sense of guilt.

Results

Does not the Greek term *genesis* (γένεσις) mean “origin” or “birth”?... During nearly three weeks of analysis – sustained preconsciously and resurfacing at times into awareness – I shifted away from a prenatal interpretation of the narrative of the original transgression. Likely due to a resistance to reflecting on *birth* – the natural outcome of one’s time in the womb – the round, firm

“apple” came to symbolise, at times, the testicles and, at others, the mother’s breast and the infant’s emerging teeth, required to bite into the apple – suggesting that the infant’s “sin” might be nibbling on the mother while nursing, punished by weaning. But then, noticing that the apple bears far less resemblance to the mother’s breast than the pear does, and reflecting on what other meaning the apple might hold, I realised that this symbol transcends the merely feminine or maternal to primarily signify the *child’s navel* (Figures 1-4, pp. 49-66 ¹), while the serpent stands for the *umbilical cord* rather than simply the penis (Figure 5, pp. 67-69). This reframed the punishment for our “Original Sin” as

¹ In the interest of readability, all figures – some with captions and image credits extending over several pages and, on occasion, multiple conveying the same idea – are assembled in an *Illustrations* section at the close of the essay (pp. 47-160). In the text, they are cited by number with the corresponding page or page range indicated, thereby permitting consultation without disrupting the stream of thought.

the cutting of the umbilical cord — a severance that marked the point of no return in our expulsion from the intrauterine paradise.

Discussion

The Death of the Body

Why would the unconscious equate the uterus with Paradise and see the cutting of the umbilical cord as punishment? Intrauterine life was “eternal”; for a child facing death, the dead are sleepers who have stopped breathing. This infantile belief links death to breathing: we die because our mothers can no longer breathe for both themselves and us. From this arises an interpretation of death — as the result of cutting the cord — as punishment for having brought our mothers to the threshold of death in the act of birth: a punishment inflicted both on the child and on the culpable cord that caused the pangs of labour by nourishing the apple-foetus; a wound whose vestige is the apple’s navel-like cavity.

Freud (1915b, p. 289) wrote that it is “impossible to imagine our own death”. This is true with respect to the cessation of

consciousness, a state incompatible with imagination: consciousness cannot become conscious of the extinction of consciousness. By contrast, we can imagine the death of the body—its subsequent decomposition—and it terrifies us precisely because our experience of continuous consciousness offers no psychological distance from it. When a child first confronts the idea of bodily death, they may react with strong aversion and form the fantasy of returning to the maternal womb—specifically, of restoring the cord whose severing made them dependent on breathing for survival: if one could live without breathing, the body would no longer be vulnerable to the consequences of breathlessness. Yet such a restoration is impossible; death is inevitable. Why, then, was my cord severed? Why must I die? Because my birth made my mother suffer. Human beings like Tristan (Thomas of Britain, c. 1170, p. 25) and many others — particularly in the distant past — not only inflicted atrocious suffering on their mothers, but in effect “killed” them at birth, thereby transforming humanity’s first sin into an act of matricide rather than an Oedipal one. Yet, did Oedipus kill only

his father, or also his mother (Sophocles, ca. 430 BCE, pp. 154 and 162, vv. 1176 and 1235)?...

A Response to Early Objections

First of all, it must be clearly understood that my thesis does not constitute, nor does it aspire to constitute, a justification of homosexuality. On the contrary, one of its most significant applications may lie precisely in the treatment of homosexuals, most of whom may, in truth, be curable. I insist on this point because I was surprised to discover that some of the very first remarks I received, upon disclosing certain aspects of my interpretation, associated my reading of the Fall and my emphasis on Oedipal matricide with homosexuality. One of my earliest interlocutors even urged me to remain confined within my “chapel”. Another found himself especially unsettled by my proposal that the apple symbolizes not only the feminine, but also the masculine navel. From this he hastily concluded that my theory must justify homosexuality. Such interpretations are entirely mistaken. First, my analysis of the indirect murder of Oedipus’

mother by her son (Sophocles, ca. 430 BCE, p. 162, v. 1235) does not principally concern the so-called negative Oedipus complex, in which the son rivals his mother for the father. Rather, it refers to the primordial murder of the mother through the act of birth itself. Second, when I say that the apple signifies the navel – whether that of a seductive woman or that of a man – I do not thereby assign it a purely sexual meaning. Quite the opposite: I mean, clearly and unambiguity, that the female’s navel – and *a fortiori* the male’s – is not a mere sexual emblem, but rather the mark of separation from the mother. To be sure, the male’s navel may also be perceived as a symbol of masculine seduction; yet if you cease to feel guilty for having been born of a woman; if you cease to be pathologically bound to your mother by a psychic umbilical cord, you would perceive neither in the male’s navel nor in the female’s a sexual emblem, but only the bare sign of individuation.

It is widely acknowledged that homosexual men remain pathologically attached to their mothers. Is sexual attraction between two men, each endowed with a penis, to be understood

as anything more than a caricatural yearning to reunite the two ends of a severed cord? My theory thus bears the potential to liberate men from this unnatural bond. Its purpose is not to justify homosexuality, but rather to provide a way of treating it. This must be clearly understood by my readers, before all else.

A Theory to Overcome the Oedipal Complex at its Deepest Roots

No more than that of man, the navel of woman is not a mere token of sexuality, but a mark of separation from her own mother. A mature sexual union between man and woman has nothing to do with their navels, at least physically: such a union can engender an umbilical cord between mother and child, not between wife and husband. As I shall later explain in detail, the paramount application of my theory lies in overcoming the Oedipal complex.

Why is the umbilicus seductive? In *The Trauma of Birth*, Otto Rank (1924) never addressed the severing of the umbilical cord; yet what he wrote about the desire to return to the uterus – desire in which Freud (1905, p. 226) discerned a biological foundation for the Oedipal complex – ultimately implies that the

deepest aim of infantile sexuality is to reunite the severed cord. This is why the navel symbolises sexual seduction, and why the present theory, by liberating us from the guilt of birth that feeds the longing to return to the womb, offers a way to overcome the Oedipal complex at its deepest roots.

“Mother died today. Or, maybe, yesterday; I can’t be sure.”

Many mothers, particularly in former times, perished in childbirth, and Eve – whose death the Scripture leave unrecorded – may likewise have expired giving birth to her lastborn. When a mother dies in childbirth, she can no longer breathe for herself and for her child, even if the umbilical cord remains uncut, which further deepens the association between our birth and our death. Even those whose mother did not die in giving them birth may feel guilty of matricide; like Edgar Allan Poe (1835, p. 19), whose mother died when he was two years of age, they can declare: “Here died my mother. Herein was I born” – for the simple reason that they will outlive their mother; and they feel guilty of matricide at every moment (cf. the title of this section; Camus, 1942, p. 1), with every

breath. They know that, as a rule, parents die before their children; and their unconscious, which, as Freud (1915, p. 187) observed, knows nothing of time, construes the children's survival of their mother's death as a birth in the course of which the mother expired.

Did They Know?

Albrecht Dürer appears to have been aware of the symbolic connection between the stem-cavity of the apple and the human navel. In two depictions of original sin, he oriented the fruit cavities in ways that seem deliberately aligned with the positioning of navels and anuses (Figure 6, pp. 70–71, Images 1 and 2). Nor was Dürer alone: in assembling illustrations for the present work, I was astonished by a medieval opus (Figure 6.3, p. 70) wherein the portion of Christ's belly surrounding the navel is fashioned in the likeness of an apple, as in the Neolithic effigy of Figure 2.7 (p. 53). Moreover, Middle Eastern artists of the High Middle Ages not only depicted a stylised heart on Eve's lower abdomen, placing the navel at the concavity at the top of the heart, as if to suggest that

the apple of love corresponds to the belly (Figure 13, p. 103–121, Image 2), but even adorned Adam’s lower abdomen with the form of an apple, aligning the fruit’s stem-cavity with Adam’s navel (Figure 7, pp. 72–73).

The Terrestrial Paradise symbolises the Womb of the Mother

The word *paradise* derives from the Old Persian *pairidaēza*, “compounded of *pairi*, ‘around’, and *daēza*, ‘wall’”, and signifying “an enclosure” (Klein, 1971, p. 533), an “enclosed park” (Weekley, 1921, p. 1039). Although this scientific etymology does not link *paradise* to *para* – meaning “beside” or “contrary to”, as in *paradox* – nor to *dis* – which conveys the idea of “separation”, as in *disconnect* – it is not unscientific to hypothesise that these morphemes may have exerted a subtle influence on the shaping of the word’s final form: *paradis* in French, *paradise* in English. The term thus seems to evoke a safe, walled space where the umbilical cord *cannot (para) be cut (dis)*, and where scarcely any harm can befall the foetus, who therefore dwells as if in a religious “Paradise”. Even if *para* and *dis* bore no relation to *paradise*, the

very notion of *enclosure* evokes the uterine wall (Figure 8, pp. 74–76).

The serpent mirrors the umbilical cord in shape and function

In the biblical narrative of the Fall, the serpent is a composite figure: the father’s symbolic phallus, yet simultaneously the child’s umbilical cord, signifying it not merely by form but also by function. Alongside the fruit stalk, the serpent embodies the cord that nourishes the foetus, as it nourished Adam with the apple. Yet, on the reverse of this symbolic coin, the serpent – renowned for its wisdom (Genesis 3:1; see especially Hooke, 1949, p. 152; and Matthew 10:16) – also evokes the skillful severer of the cord: the midwife, *la sage-femme* in French, literally the “wise woman”, whose task cannot be accomplished by the stalk. Through its characteristic *hiss*, the serpent evokes the aerial breath that follows the cutting of the cord. In matters of “temptation”, the serpent acts as an agent of union – phallic from the father’s side, umbilical with respect to the child – wisely bringing forth the cord to sever it in the guise of the *sage-femme*.

The Fall Narrative and the Art of Belly Dance

The interpretation of the forbidden apple as a symbol of feminine sexuality often derives from its resemblance to the rounded contours of the female body – particularly the breasts and buttocks. Yet, to my knowledge, the striking parallel between the stem-cavity of the apple of seduction and the navel of the ‘belly dancer’ (Figure 9, pp. 77–81) has been largely overlooked. Despite the longstanding association of apples and other fruits with fecundity – a term denoting the fertility of land as well as that of animals and humans, and occasionally rendered as “fruitfulness” in reference to humans (Tempest, 1709, p. 29, Fig. 116, and Ripa, 1603, Fig. p. 225, where a woman’s fruitfulness is symbolised by a nest held near her womb) – the link between the apple and the human navel, whether male or female, has remained equally ignored.

A painter once depicted a belly dancer whose navel was covered by a jewel in the form of a cross (Figure 9.7, p. 77), explicitly linking the memory of birth to original sin – a connection

that recalls the resemblance between the posture of the crucified, arms outstretched, and the uterus with its two Fallopian tubes. The navel, however — let me stress — is not merely a symbol of sexual reproduction and the Augustinian inheritance of sin; above all, it serves as a reminder of *birth itself*. As witness, the ancient ‘*almeh*’ — precursor of the less esteemed belly dancer — was associated alike with *culture* and with *procreation*, and not only with sex.

Oriental belly dance traces its origins to the Harems — intimate, protected spaces within Middle Eastern households where women gathered. While it is uncertain whether the ‘*awālim*’ exposed their bellies while dancing in the harems, it is certain that these dancers were respected; even after their transition from the Harem to dance before men, they were far from being “fallen women”.

The latter expression, which appears to use the adjective “fallen” as a reference to the narrative of the Fall, is drawn from Edward Said’s homage to the 20th-century Egyptian dancer Tahia Carioca (homage mentioned in the Wikipedia article “*Almah*”). Distinguishing the origins of *la danse du ventre* — meaning “belly

dance”, a term pejoratively coined in France during the late 19th century, either by Jean-Léon Gérôme or by critics of his painting titled *Dance of the Almeh* (Hawthorn, 2020) who was, in fact, a *ghaziya* performing publicly likely for payment and without the distinction of erudition (Wikipedia, art. “*Ghawazi*”) – from “striptease”, Said (1990) wrote: “Tahia [adopted] the all-but-forgotten role of *almeh* (literally, a learned woman), spoken of by 19th-century European visitors to the Orient such as Edward Lane and Flaubert. The *almeh* was a courtesan of sorts, but a woman of significant accomplishments. Dancing was only one of her gifts: others were the ability to sing and recite classical poetry, to discourse wittily, to be sought after for her company by men of law, politics and literature”.

The *‘awālim* (plural of *‘almeh*, or *‘almah*, a term derived from the Arabic word *‘alima*, meaning *wise*, learned woman) were educated girls of good social order. Trained in poetry, singing and dancing, they were “present at festivals and entertainments, and [...] hired [as] mourners at funerals” (*Encyclopædia Britannica*, 1911). They were not merely entertainers, but also educators and

caretakers. In the Harems, they entertained and instructed women, teaching good manners, the art of cosmetics, dance, and song. In a word, they were scarcely less learned, or “wise”, than the serpent of Genesis, and beyond their artistic and educational roles, the ‘*awālīm* are also said to have served as... *midwives* (Musée des Beaux-Arts Jules Chéret, n.d.), with some even claiming that mothers would attend belly dancers’ performances to identify “strong and supple” brides for their sons, thereby ensuring the vitality of future generations (Brewer, 2024).

“Weddings, evaluating prospective brides... there are strong elements and associations with fertility in the traditions of belly dance, and this gives a hint of where and how these dances originated. It’s not for nothing that the Hebrew root word meaning ‘to dance’ can also mean ‘to writhe in labour and childbirth’ and ‘to shake or tremble’ (that’s obviously belly dancing!).

“Many of the movements that are characteristic of belly dance involve quintessentially feminine parts of the body: the pelvis, the hips, the thighs, the abdomen and the buttocks. This has led many to believe that the dance style had its origins as exercises to

strengthen and prepare women for labour and childbirth or motions to assist during childbirth itself, or possibly as rites to honour goddesses of fertility – or both! The truth is that nobody really knows for certain. However, it’s certainly true that belly dancing is very good exercise for pregnant women, and celebrates the feminine parts of the body”.

This long excerpt from Brewer’s historical account of Belly Dance illustrates the extent to which the origin of this dance is respectable, and how the “apple”, as a symbol of seduction, relates to birth. In its original context, the belly dance was a symbol of culture and artistry, celebrating the feminine form and its profound connection to life and (pro)creation. As time passed, those women began performing before men; erudition was no longer a prerequisite for all dancers, and their attire evolved to become progressively more revealing, with the exposed navel emerging as a signature feature. This shift cast female dancers as figures of decadence and even prostitution, much as Eve’s sexuality was construed as evil, as though it were not part of her maternal role.

The Dance of Death

The *'almeh* evokes Scheherazade of *The Thousand and One Nights*, who, through her erudition, saved her life and transformed her fated union with Shahryar into one of love and motherhood (Anonymous, 9th-14th century, p. 51). On the darker side of the same coin, the *'almeh* also calls to mind Salomé, whose dance before her stepfather led to the decapitation of John the Baptist (Figure 10, pp. 82-83). In *The Last Day of a Condemned Man*, Victor Hugo conceived the expulsion from Paradise as a kind of decapitation (Hugo, 1832, p. 236; cf. Genesis 2:17). The Baptist's beheading, closely linked with a serpentine dance, may be understood as the severing of the umbilical cord. This supports my view that human death, conceived as the cessation of breath, is interpreted as the consequence of the cord's severing in punishment for the pains of childbirth. In the case of a great passion such as that of Jesus, punishment is transfigured into redemption. Though it is still early to fully develop my interpretation of the Crucifixion in light of the Fall narrative, I can

already say this: baptism may be understood as the washing away of the maternal blood that once covered the newborn, and Jesus's Crucifixion stands as the expiation for the "sin" of birth.

Adam does not have a mother; Cain Does

Unquestionably, as a religious figure and the first man, our most revered ancestor Adam has, in reality, no mother — nor does our first mother, Eve. They are simply the very first man and his wife. Yet from a psychoanalytic and symbolic perspective, Adam and Eve may be understood as representations of each of us. In this symbolic register, Adam and Eve appear as children born of mothers. Undoubtedly, Eve is not the mother of the first man; yet the verse in Genesis that names her "the mother of all living" (Genesis 3:20) implies that she is symbolically — let me stress, symbolically, not literally — the "mother" of every human being, including the first, who is both present in, and representative of, all those born of him.

Far from constituting any Freudian offense against the venerable Adam and his wife, the notion that Adam and Eve

symbolise every man and every woman born of a mother merely implies that Eve stands for every mother and every mother's daughter, and Adam for every mother's *son* – nothing more. This interpretation accords with the Christian doctrine that identifies Jesus as the new Adam and his mother Mary as the new Eve (1 Corinthians 15:45; John 2:4; John 19:26; Irenaeus of Lyons, ca. 180 CE: a, pp. 296 and 494; b, pp. 99-100; *Catechism of the Catholic Church*, n.d., § 494). Though this doctrine casts the first man as a son and the first woman as a mother, it in no way dishonours Adam and Eve, for the designation remains purely *symbolic*.

Cain – the first born from Adam and Eve – is not absent from the narrative of the Fall: he is entwined with Adam; he is present in Adam's semence; he is – symbolically – the very “apple” eaten by Eve. From this perspective, when I speak of the apple as representing the child's navel, I refer, above all, to the navel of Cain.

Though Adam and Cain are oedipally interwoven, the navel and the umbilical cord – figured by the apple and the serpent –

do not pertain to the true Adam, who had no mother, but to the firstborn of Eve. This son, who in some measure reflects the father, also stands apart from him: he represents the father, is represented by him in artistic depictions of original sin, and yet ultimately diverges. The apple, with its erotic resonance, inclines toward the father, yet as a navel, it belongs to the son — and marks his difference. Unmistakably, the serpent symbolises the *paternal* phallus, though it also symbolises the umbilical cord that binds the child to the mother. Thus, for all that father and son are reflected in one another, they remain irreducibly distinct. In sum, when understood as a navel, the apple signifies the bond between Cain and his mother, Eve, and must not be taken to imply that Adam is bound to Eve by flesh (Figures 11–15, pp. 84–133).

In Ancient Greece, the apple symbolised not only sexuality but also the noble idea of procreation (Freeman, 1926, p. 119), as in *The Arnolfini Portrait* and in *Eve* of the Ghent Altarpiece (referenced as Figures 11.7 and 8). In the narrative of the Fall, the apple most of all signifies Cain, who — by “eating” his own body-“fruit” from the maternal tree (de Balzac, 1847, p. 12) — is born as

the “fruit”, that is, the product (de Balzac, 1847, pp. 117 and 149) of the sexual union between Adam and Eve.

Like his Mrs Arnolfini, Jan van Eyck’s Eve seems to bear the signs of pregnancy at the very moment of sin. This woman assumes dual roles: sexually, she is Adam’s wife; beyond sexuality, she is the mother of the children who shall arise from her union with the first man, who, himself, has no mother. This view is depicted in Figure 11.5 (p. 84), where Eve is portrayed as the mother of Adam’s children before all else. Viewed in this light, the man in Figure 2.1 (p. 53) represents not only Adam but also his firstborn, Cain, who was “in germ” inside of him. This interpretation resonates with the ancient belief of “animalculism” (Rostand, 1945, p. 25-26), as well as with the notion that Cain, the eldest son of Adam and Eve, demonstrated a preference for *fruits* over animals (Genesis 4:1-5). This interpretation is also supported by the fact that, “though Cain, the son of Adam and Eve, was born after the expulsion from paradise, the [author of Figure 11.5 depicted] the infant in the arms of the fleeing couple” (Philadelphia Museum of Art, n.d.). Let us also note that God’s

preference for animal offerings over those of fruit signifies that the development of the fruit-embryo and its birth represent a sin not only against the mother but also against God “the Father”. This echoes the Greek myth in which Oedipus’s father, alarmed *before his son’s birth* (Sophocles, ca. 430 BCE, v. 714, pp. 100–101, and note p. 100) by the oracle’s prophecy, sought to prevent his son’s *birth*.

Many Artists Represented Adam and Eve with Three Apples

Where one might expect a simple pair – one apple for Eve, one for Adam – artists frequently rendered the biblical Fall with three or more apples, notably varying in size. As I observed in my commentary on Figure 12 (pp. 96–97), these may signify distinct moments within the act of sinning – successive stages in the apple’s passage from serpent to Adam. However, the third, smaller apple may also represent the future Cain (Figure 16, pp. 134–142).

Eve's Punishment as Mother and as Newborn

In Genesis 3:16, it is said that the punishment of the woman for eating from the “tree of the knowledge” was to suffer the pains of childbirth. Here, the fruit symbolises the entire foetus, not particularly its navel – a foetus that the father’s snake-penis caused to be “ingested” by the mother (a well-known infantile sexual theory: Freud, 1905, p. 196), who, as punishment for her sexual appetite, would suffer the pains of childbirth. This was her punishment as a *woman*; yet the focus on Eve’s status as a woman both reveals and attempts to veil her punishment as a *girl* standing for every *daughter*. The fruit that the daughter, like the son, ate, also represents the entire foetus, but here, it signifies the *self* as a foetus: here, the fruit does not symbolise the *foetus of the mother*, but rather the personal body of the foetus itself. “Adam” – that is, at bottom, Cain – like “Eve”, as daughter, appropriated a body by “eating” the body-“apple” from the maternal “tree” through the snake-peduncle-cord that connected the foetus to the “tree of the knowledge”, or “tree of life”, a term which in biology designates

the vascular “tree” of the placenta (cf. *infra*, pp. 36–39 where I argue that the two trees are materially one and the same).

Adam and Eve’s primal sin is not sexuality, which leads to pregnancy, but rather causing harm to the mother by “eating” from her body; their sin is to have caused the pains of pregnancy, which reach their peak in the pains of childbirth and are punished by cutting the cord, the mark of which is the apple-cavity-navel. Sexuality is perceived as “bad” because it provokes the pains of childbirth and death. Labour throes are not truly “punishments”, but *reasons* why sexuality is burdened with guilt, primarily toward the mother. Here, we are in the presence of a Freudian “*reversal*” (Freud, 1900, p. 288) of crime and punishment. The true “punishments” are not the pains of childbirth, but the “mortal” severing of the cord and castration. This sense of guilt ought to be lessened by mitigating the association between cord-cutting and death, as well as between cord-cutting and the pains of childbirth. Such associations nourish the Oedipus and the feeling of guilt toward both parents — let me stress: toward *both* father and mother, as I shall discuss at length in the second part of this

essay – for Oedipus, after all, slew both « νιν τοὺς τεκόντας » (Sophocles, ca. 430 BCE, p. 154, v. 1176): “the ones who begot him” – his *parents* – not only his father...

Created or Born

In the narrative of the Fall, Adam – though motherless – is assimilated to Cain, who has one, through the notion that Nature itself is Adam’s mother. Nature, however, does not give birth in the literal sense; and, according to Scripture, Adam was created before Eve. How, then, are we to reconcile these facts with the interpretation that Eve, in a certain manner, gave birth to the father under the figure of the son, who is the reflection of the first, the image of his own beginning?

The answer is that we are here faced once more with a Freudian reversal, a well-known mechanism of dream-work in which an element is “represented by its reverse” (Freud, 1900, p. 288). More precisely, it is here a reversal of *roles*: as Freud illustrates, “In [Alphonse Daudet’s (1884)] *Sappho* the man carried a woman who was in a sexual relation to him; in the dream-

thoughts the position was *reversed*, and a woman was carrying a man”. The biblical account of Eve’s creation enacts the same logic – one that inverts the natural direction of birth (Figure 17, pp. 143-145). As I noted earlier, a similar mechanism of reversal also explains why, in the manifest content of the biblical narrative, the pains of childbirth are presented as punishment for sin (Genesis 3:16), whereas in truth the very notion of sin originates in the guilt of having injured the mother through the act of being born.

Genesis as Birth

Figure 18 (pp. 146-149) reveals the hidden connection between the narrative of the Fall and the theme of birth through the motif of the hair whorl. Positioned on the apex of the head – the first part of the body to emerge at birth – the hair whorl is depicted in a manner that evokes the navel in two representations: one of the expulsion of Adam and Eve from Paradise, and the other of a birth chamber. This connection between Fall and birth is further reinforced by the fact that the navels of Eve, that of an angel, and even that of “God” are strangely visible through their garments in

two representations of the expulsion from Paradise, while Adam's navel is clearly depicted on his garment in a representation where Eve's hair is veiled. The veil on Eve's hair suggests a symbolic connection between original sin – which brought about the awareness of nudity – and hair: a link between original sin and the umbilical cord that the hair represents.

“Blessed are you among women, and blessed is the fruit of your womb” (Luke 1:42) : The Fleshly “Apple”

Owing to their rounded form, the zygote, the morula, the blastocyst – and even, at a later stage, the embryonic disc with its amniotic cavity and yolk sac – closely resemble an apple (Figure 19, pp. 150-154, Images 1-3). More broadly, the embryo, together with these cavities, all enclosed within the extraembryonic coelom – and later the foetus, encased within the rounded amnion filled with fluid, imparting to the mother's belly its characteristic curvature – resemble a fruit in their overall form throughout gestation (Figure 19.2-6, p. 150). Bound to the maternal body – first via the body stalk (Figure 19.2 and 3), then via the umbilical

cord (Figure 19.4-12) – the embryo recalls a fruit not only in its rounded form but also through the analogy between these connectors and a fruit’s stem. As development advances, the embryo gradually relinquishes its spherical shape and begins to take on the appearance of a tree, with the neck, arms, and legs unfurling like branches. Nevertheless, particularly after the severing of the cord, the abdominal region retains throughout life its likeness to an apple – by virtue of the analogy between the umbilicus and the apple’s stem-cavity.

There is even a stage in normal embryonic development during which the abdomen bears a striking resemblance to that of the Greek figurine presented in Figure 2.7 (p. 53). This natural phenomenon, known as “physiologic midgut herniation”, occurs around the fourth week of development and persists until approximately the thirteenth week of gestation: during this period, the rapid growth of the embryonic midgut – outpacing that of the abdominal cavity – leads to a herniation of the bowel into the base of the umbilical cord. This herniation appears as a pronounced bulge at the site where the cord inserts into the abdomen (Figure

19.7-10, p. 150). Between the tenth and thirteenth weeks, as the abdominal cavity expands and the intestines return to their rightful place, the site of insertion returns to normal (Figure 19.11-12) – just as if the child had eaten, through the cord, the fruit that once rested on its belly.

Did the creator of that Greek figurine, and the author of the narrative of the Fall of Man, once see aborted embryos during the stage of development in which a physiological midgut herniation creates the appearance of a round fruit nestled at the junction between the umbilical cord and the abdomen? They would also surely have observed, in newborns, that the abdomen bears no such hernia and appears entirely normal – and perhaps noted, consciously or not, that the remnant of the severed cord closely resembles the stem-cavity of an apple. Might they have concluded, then, that the “fruit” enclosed within the umbilical cord of the embryo is, more precisely, an apple – and that embryos acquire their bodies by ingesting “apples” through the cords?

Although the biblical author speaks only of a “fruit” and never names the apple outright, it was likely the belly’s resemblance to

an apple in particular that stirred his imagination when composing the story. He imagined the embryo as feeding on the apple — an idea the sculptor of the figurine, though aware that the newborn’s abdomen bears no trace of herniation, sought to emphasise by placing an apple at the very centre of the man’s belly. Perhaps they also imagined that the aborted embryos they had seen had died of obstruction of the cord by the apple — and that embryos do not complete their development, nor are they born, until they have fully swallowed the apple without obstruction.

The tree symbolises the human body. It is most closely associated with the body of the mother, as she contributes the largest part to the body of the children-fruits. The fruit is primarily linked to the embryo, for as the embryo grows, it increasingly resembles a tree rather than an apple (Figure 19.13, p. 150), particularly when the child reaches adulthood (Figures 19.14 and 15). Nonetheless, the adult human body is no less akin to a fruit than the embryo. The child, whether boy or girl, “eats the apple” — that is, assumes the body — and his navel remains, unto death, akin to the apple’s stem-cavity. These correspondances are

reflected in Dürer's portrayal of the newborn Jesus (Figure 19.13, p. 150) who cradles an apple (see also Figure 20, pp. 155-157), in the exactly same manner as the adult Eve holds the apple in her left arm in Figure 12.1 (p. 89). When Jesus reached adulthood, his body – by then more akin to a tree (Figure 19.14, p. 150), yet still bearing the likeness of the forbidden fruit – was crucified upon “the tree of the knowledge” as a means of atoning for the “sin” of childbirth pains borne by the adult body-tree of Mary or Eve as mother figures...

Knowledge is Life

One might object that, in the Bible, the forbidden “tree of the knowledge of good and evil” differs from the “tree of life”, which grants immortality and represents, in my view, the placental vessels. To respond to this objection, I would readily show that the distinction between the two trees lacks evidence. A visual expression of this ambiguity appears on the front cover of a Routledge reprint of *The Trauma of Birth* (Rank, 1924). Scripture itself proves no less ambiguous on this distinction. God expelled

Adam and Eve from paradise to prevent them from eating “also” (Genesis 3:22) from the “tree of life”. The word “also” may imply that the “tree of life” is different from the “tree of the knowledge”, but it may also be understood to mean “again”, suggesting that Adam and Eve were expelled from paradise to prevent them from eating *once more* (again) from the “tree of life”, which is the same as the “tree of the knowledge”. Did God prevent Adam and Eve from eating *more* from the “tree of the knowledge” so that foetuses would not grow even larger and cause even more harm to their mothers during birth? If the “tree of the knowledge” was not truly the same as the biblical “tree of life”, we might consider that the latter, from which Adam and Eve were allowed to eat without dying, is a spiritual tree producing *immaterial* food. But even at the material level, the biblical “tree of life” reflects the biological “tree of life” understood as the immortality of the species — that is, the collective perpetuation of life. From this perspective, our Original Sin is tied to *generational rivalry* whether between the child and the mother or the child and the father: primary and secondary

Oedipal rivalries, but also competition over longevity itself (Genesis 3:22).

At the individual level too, the “tree of life” is the “tree of the knowledge” whose fruits’ stem-cavities resemble the human navel. “Even though no sources specify that [in Ancient Greece] the golden apples conferred immortality or youth, their divine associations and location in the paradise-like garden of the gods relate to Heracles’ attainment of immortality and the pleasures of a blessed afterlife” (Salapata, 2021, p. 151). Reflecting at least her own association of the navel with longevity, another writer asserts that “legends [for which I have found no truly reliable references, even] said that many of Alexander’s priests lived as long as four hundred years because they consumed only apples” (Bennett, 2024; those priests lived not very much less than Adam: Genesis 5:5). The medieval Arabic work “*The Book of The Apple* (Risalat alTuffaha, [ca. 900 CE]), which was known in the West by the long-winded Latin title of *Tractatus de pomo et morte incliti principis philosophorum Aristotelis* [...], portrays the dying Aristotle discoursing on immortality while occasionally reviving

himself with the *smell* of an apple” (Netton, 1991, p. 31; my italics). Aristotle, ascribed as the author, said: “I will disobey the advice of the physician, and will employ no drug but the *scent* of an apple; which will keep me alive till I have given you the lecture to which you have a right” (Margoliouth, 1892, pp. 230–231; emphasis added to highlight the link between the “apple” and breath through the sense of smell). Even the author of the Song of Songs invokes the image of a lovesick woman imploring to be revived “with apples” (Solomon, uncertain date, p. 952. The Song of Solomon 2:5). All this, along with the English pseudoscientific proverb “An apple a day keeps the doctor away”, supports the idea that the apple “tree of the knowledge” is also a “tree of life” – a placental “tree” providing infantile “immortality” (cf. *supra*, p. 9).

The Apple: Archetype of Fruit

Another objection arises from the fact that Scripture gives no indication of the species of “the tree of the knowledge of good and evil”. It speaks only of a forbidden fruit, not explicitly of an apple – a textual indeterminacy that has moved some to see in that fruit

the fig, others the peach, and yet others even the pear. All fruits possess-stem cavities, though it is that of the apple which most closely resembles the human belly. The apple, however, is regarded as the fruit *par excellence*, as reflected in the etymology of the French word *pomme*, which derives not from the Latin *malum*, meaning “apple”, but from *pomum*, a term that designates any kind of *fruit* (Bloch and von Wartburg, 1932, p. 498). The apple’s elevation to the status of the fruit *par excellence* was likely inspired by its striking resemblance to the belly – a symbolic echo that may also explain why Latin contains two nearly homonymous words: *malum*, with a short *a*, meaning “apple”, and *mālum*, with a long *a*, meaning “evil”. This suggests that the association of the forbidden fruit with the apple, in the imagination of newly Christianized Latins, arose not merely from a pun on *malum* and *mālum*, but from a far older connection – one that reaches back into the pagan world, where the apple was already linked to evil precisely because of its likeness to the belly. Such beliefs are attested among certain African peoples, for whom “evil is thought to reside in the belly” (Littleton, 2002, p. 641), and among

Egyptians, who, as Plutarch (1st c. CE, p. 563) recounts, “extract the viscera of the dead and cut them open in view of the sun, then throw them away as being the cause of every single sin that the man had committed”.

The Secret Navel

After all, is it not almost explicitly stated in Scripture that the forbidden fruit represents the offspring? Pyyhtinen (2014, p. 1) observes that “in the mythical origin of humankind, the birth of human collectivity is closely woven with [...] an apple”, which “created the very first human relation”. And he beautifully remarks that “The myth places the apple, the fruit of ‘the tree of the knowledge of good and evil’, in the green boughs of the *family tree* [my emphasis] of humankind or, better perhaps, at its roots”. Does not this mean that the “apple” is nothing other than one’s own body? But let me conclude this Part I with the prodigious Figure 21 (pp. 158-160), in which Adam holds the apple precisely before his belly, its stem-cavity oriented toward the viewer at nearly the

exact position of the navel, as though to cover it were to symbolise it. *Did they know?*²

Récapitulation

I shall further recapitulate this part with a concise account of the latent content of the Fall narrative:

In the renowned narrative of Adam and Eve, the name “Adam” likewise designates the foetus Cain. With his eyes, the man Adam “consumes” the rounded forms of Eve’s body; the vision kindles desire, and Adam’s “serpent”-phallus compels Eve to “ingest” the embryo, which takes the likeness of an apple. The Cain-embryo is nourished through the fruit peduncle-“serpent”-umbilical cord: he appropriates a body by consuming the “apple”. This act was reckoned a “sin”, for it brought travail and suffering upon the mother (Janov, 1973, p. 76), and even death in childbirth. The sin of birth is punished by the severing of the umbilical cord, an act felt cruel, for, in the child’s perception, human mortality derives from aerial respiration: had our mothers been able to breathe perpetually for themselves and for us, we

might have partaken of immortality, as in Paradise. Perhaps death itself is apprehended as evil precisely because it is conceived both as punishment and as inextricably entwined with the pangs of parturition. Ultimately, the “Fall” of Man is naught but the fall of an “apple” from the womb.

This psychoanalytic reading of the Fall of Man finds its natural prolongation in that of the Passion of Christ, which ought not to be regarded merely as an expiation of Oedipal guilt, as Freud proposed. The infant Jesus — never the adolescent or adult — is frequently depicted with an apple. He came to liberate the descendants of Adam from Adam’s transgression (Matthew 20:28; Romans 5:19; 1 Corinthians 15:21-22). Yet, unlike Adam, he is never portrayed as an adolescent or adult consuming the fruit; he appears solely as a child, making manifest that Adam, as the sinner, stands figuratively for his progeny in its childhood, while the adult crucified, as representing the penitent, embodies the adult who yet harbours within him the sinning child — and, deeper still, the sinning foetus. True redemption — the royal road to becoming

an innocent adult – consists in making conscious the sense of guilt bound up with birth.

In Part II, I shall substantiate my interpretation of the Fall narrative through Plato, Nietzsche, and other eminent thinkers; examine the relationship between the Oedipal and Adamic complexes; consider the sufferings of Christ as the expiation of the mother's pains; and finally, unveil that which seems to me to constitute the content of the primal repressed.

Illustrations ²

² Some images have been trimmed for formatting purposes. Others are not reproduced in this work but are documented in the respective lists of illustrations.

Figure 1. The apple as a bodily symbol.

The apple evokes the rounded forms of the maternal body. In Images 1 and 2, the Christ Child is depicted clasping an apple even as he draws nourishment from his mother's breast. Yet the breast resembles a pear more than an apple. The main visual difference between the pear and the apple lies not in their overall shape but in the form of the cavity where the stalk is attached. Unlike the pear, the apple has a deep stem-cavity, strongly reminiscent of the human umbilicus (Image 3). Note that in Images 4 and 5, the Virgin holds a fruit and a flower by their stalks, and that the artist left Jesus' umbilicus visible between two of the Virgin's fingers in Image 5 – the very same fingers that hold a cherry's pedicle in Image 4. In Image 6 (not reproduced here; see reference below), by contrast, it is through a different interdigital space that the artist chooses to depict the Virgin offering her mamelon to Jesus – perhaps to distinguish the nipple from the mamelon understood as the rounded prominence at the centre of the navel's depression (Image 7).

Images:

1, Jan van Eyck, *Lucca Madonna*, ca. 1437. Städel Museum, Frankfurt am Main. Image freely provided by the Museum via its online Digital Collection. Subsequent images from the same source are credited with the shortened reference: “Städel Museum, Frankfurt am Main”, as required by the Museum.

2, Joos van Cleve, *The Holy Family*, ca. 1512-13. The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York. Image released into the public domain by the Museum under its Open Access policy. Below, images from the same institution are credited in abbreviated form as: “The Met, OA”.

3, Paul Cézanne, *Grenade et poires dans une assiette* [*Pomegranate and Pears on a Plate*], ca. 1885-1890. Private collection; location unknown to the author. Photo © The Yorck Project (2002) *10.000 Meisterwerke der Malerei* (DVD-ROM), made available via Wikimedia Commons by Directmedia Publishing GmbH, abbreviated below as “The Yorck Project”.

4, Workshop of Joos van Cleve, *The Holy Family*, ca. 1525. The Met, OA.

5, Workshop of Joos van Cleve, *The Holy Family*, possibly between 1527 and 1533. The Met, OA.

6, Workshop of Rogier van der Weyden, *Virgin and Child*, ca. 1455-1465. Art Institute of Chicago. Available from:

<https://www.artic.edu/artworks/16303/virgin-and-child>

7, Figure 34.A on page 35 of *Embryology, Anatomy, and Diseases of the Umbilicus, Together with Diseases of the Urachus* written by Thomas Cullen, illustrated by Max Brödel: Philadelphia & London, W. B. Saunders Company, 1916. Digitised by Internet Archive. Available from:

<https://archive.org/details/embryologvanatom00cull/page/34/mod/e/2up?q=mamelon&view=theater>

Figure 2. The Human Navel as an Apple's Stem-Cavity: A Symbol Beyond Sexuality and Femininity.

Are four repetitions enough to show the obvious (Image 1)? As also is clearly observed in “belly dance” (Figure 9, pp. 77–81), the

navel — resembling the stem-cavity of an apple (Images 2-6) — emerges as the most potent tool of feminine seduction, consistent with the widely recognised idea that the forbidden fruit is a feminine sexual symbol. Yet the relationship between the navel and sin extends beyond the sexual, whether in its erotic guise, where the feminine navel is an instrument of seduction, or in its Augustinian sense, where the navel is the scar of birth, itself the consequence of the sexual act and the channel of “hereditary” sin; the apple symbolises not only the woman’s navel but the navel itself.

In the Farnese Hercules (Image 9), the hero conceals the apples of the Hesperides behind his back (Image 8), but he exhibits his own “apple”-belly. The French painter Paul Cézanne is celebrated for his remarkable depictions of apples, most of which are rendered entirely detached from their stems (Images 2 and 4-6), making their stem-cavities more akin to human navels, as is Caravaggio’s (Image 3). Cézanne, likely acquainted with the Farnese Hercules statue, found in the Baths of Caracalla, also depicted numerous bathers of both sexes with exceptionally

pronounced navels, many raising their right arms aloft as if to reveal, upon their abdomens, the apples that Hercules conceals behind his back in his right hand. What's more, some of Cézanne's depictions of the apple stem-cavity strikingly mirror most of his own portrayals of bathers' navels (Image 10), lending substantial weight to my hypothesis that the forbidden fruit signifies the navel.

Cézanne's interplay of apples and navels shall be the focus of a forthcoming work of mine. For now, the Greek figurine in Image 7, dating back seven thousand years before the birth of Christ, perhaps best embodies my idea. Observe how the area around the navel rises in a distinct circular form, setting it apart from the rest of the abdomen, creating the impression of an actual apple resting upon the belly. Interestingly, this statuette depicts a man, not a woman, despite "the exaggerated proportions of the hips and belly [which] have been interpreted as fertility symbols", as noted on the official webpage for the artwork. This duality suggests that the apple, rather than being tied more closely to femininity or masculinity, symbolises the navel as a mark of separation between

mother and child, whether daughter or son, and an emblem of individuation.

Images:

1, Cornelis Cornelisz van Haarlem, *De zondeval [The Fall of Man]*, 1592. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam. High-resolution image reproduced with the kind permission of the Museum. The simplified reference “Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam” is employed hereafter for other high-resolution images from the same source, in accordance with the Museum’s request.

2, Paul Cézanne, *Apples*, 1878–79, detail. The Met, OA.

3, Michelangelo Merisi da Caravaggio (attributed to), *Still Life with Fruit on a Stone Ledge*, ca. 1603, detail. Private collection; location unknown to the author. Public domain image (abbreviated below as “PDI”) from Wikimedia Commons.

4, Paul Cézanne, *Verre et pommes [Glass and Apples]*, between 1879 and 1882, detail. The Rudolf Staechelin Collection, Kunstmuseum Basel, Switzerland. PDI from Wikimedia Commons, reproduced with the Museum’s approval.

5, Paul Cézanne, *Grenade et poires dans une assiette* [*Pomegranate and Pears on a Plate*], between 1885 and 1890, detail. Private collection; location unknown to the author. The Yorck Project.

6, Paul Cézanne, *Grosses pommes* [*Big apples*], between 1890 and 1894, detail. Private collection, Washington, DC. The Yorck Project.

7, Unknown artist/maker, *Fragmentary Neolithic seated figurine* produced in northern Greece, 6th–5th millennium BCE. The J. Paul Getty Museum, Villa Collection, California. Photograph released into the public domain under Getty’s Open Content Programme. Source material available from:

<https://www.getty.edu/art/collection/object/1040A3>

Subsequent references to images from the same institution will use “Getty, Open”.

8, Detail of a photograph depicting a partial rear view of the statue presented in Image 9. Photo: Marie-Lan Nguyen, 2011 - Wikimedia Commons, CC BY 2.5.

<https://creativecommons.org/licences/by/2.5/>

9, Glykon of Athens, *Hercules at Rest* of the Farnese-Pitti type, 3rd century CE, found in the Baths of Caracalla, Rome, in 1540. After an original by Lysippos, late 4th century BCE. National Archaeological Museum, Naples. Photo: Sergey Sosnovskiy, 2006 - Wikimedia Commons, CC BY-SA 4.0. Reproduced under the same licence. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>

10, Paul Cézanne, *Bather with Outstretched Arms*, ca. 1878. Private collection; location unknown to the author. PDI from WikiArt.

Figure 3. Jesus' Apple.

Owing to its roundness and the depth of its stem-cavity, the apple evokes the belly far more than the mother's breast. Observe, here and in Figure 1.4 (p. 49), the pronounced curvature of Jesus' belly, the apple placed immediately beside it in the present image.

Image:

Martin Schongauer, *Virgin and Child with the Apple*, ca. 1470-1475. National Gallery of Art, Washington, DC. Image provided by the Museum under its open access policy, cited thereafter as: "NGA, OA".

Figure 4. Renaissance Compulsion and Symbolism.

While searching for images to illustrate my study, I recently encountered a large brownish stain – likely caused by moisture –

spreading with uncanny precision around Eve's navel (Image 1), as if to direct the viewer's gaze toward the notion that the apple symbolises this very part of the human body. This stain beautifully encapsulates the core of my thesis. Mere coincidence? Although moisture may have been the immediate cause of the stain's formation, one might wonder whether, in shaping this part of the composition, the artist was acting under certain compulsions — ones that marked this area with a subtle physical difference, thereby allowing the moisture to act with such precision.

While in the previous case the navel is underscored by the coinciding effects of moisture and unconscious impulse, in some other representations of original sin — such as Images 2 and 4 — its prominence appears more deliberate, as though the artist intended to suggest the apple's hidden meaning (see also Images 5-10 and most notably Image 11).

Alongside the somewhat playful remark about the stain highlighting Eve's navel in Image 1, I feel permitted to make another observation — this time linking the theme of original sin to a self-portrait by Albrecht Dürer (Image 3). At first glance, this

drawing may appear entirely unrelated to Dürer's depictions of the Fall of Man. Sometime between 1506 and 1521 – long before the advent of photography and digital communication – Dürer, amid several episodes of unexplained illness (speculated to include mental distress, or even poisoning by rivals), created this visual message of his suffering to send to a distant physician he had consulted (Schott, 2004). *The Sick Dürer* – a remarkably early example of pain mapping – indicates the precise site of his pain with a yellow spot and a pointing finger. Yet during this same period, Dürer produced several depictions of original sin, suggesting a preoccupation – if not consciously, then at least preconsciously – with the theme. Notably, the yellow spot in *The Sick Dürer* bears a striking resemblance to an apple. This allusion might explain Dürer's choice to colour the site of his pain, which could have remained colourless without diminishing the medical message: unlike the spleen (which actually lies higher) or the intestines, which are never yellow, the apple matches the hue. Moreover, the pointing finger enters the spot at a depth uncannily similar to that of placing a finger into the stem-cavity of an apple

or in the external ear, itself resembling a foetus whose navel coincides with the ear's orifice. Thus, it may be considered that Dürer – who might well have contented himself with the spot – was, perhaps unconsciously, intimating through both colour and finger that the stem-cavity of the forbidden apple symbolises the navel, located near the yellow spot in the portrait.

Images:

1, Lucas van Leyden, *Der Sündenfall [The Fall into Sin]*, 1528.

Photo Credit: bpk | Hamburger Kunsthalle | Christoph Irrgang.

2, Heinrich Aldegrever, *Eve with a Stag*, 16th century. The Met,

OA.

3, Albrecht Dürer, *Selbstbildnis, krank [Self-portrait, ill]*, probably

ca. 1506–1507. Kunsthalle Bremen - The Kunstverein in Bremen,

Germany. Photo: Die Kulturgutscanner (The Cultural Heritage

Scanners), Public Domain Mark 1.0.

4, Heinrich Aldegrever, *Adam mit einer Ziege [Adam with a goat]*,

1551. Kunsthalle Bremen - The Kunstverein in Bremen,

Germany. Image made available by the Museum under PDM 1.0.

<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/>

5, Heinrich Aldegrever, *Gott verbietet Adam und Eva vom Baum der Erkenntnis zu essen* (blatt 2 der Folge “Geschichte von Adam und Eva”) [*God forbids Adam and Eve to eat from the Tree of Knowledge* (plate 2 from the series “The Story of Adam and Eve”)], 1540. Kunsthalle Bremen - The Kunstverein in Bremen, Germany. Available from:

<https://onlinekatalog.kunsthalle-bremen.de/DE-MUS-027614/object/41713>

6, Hans Baldung Grien, *Adam and Eve*, 1519. NGA, OA. Available from: <https://www.nga.gov/artworks/4143-adam-and-eve>

7, Caliaro Carlo, *Tentazione e Caduta di Adamo e Eva* [*The Temptation and Fall of Adam and Eve*], ca. 1586. Uffizi Galleries, Florence. Available from:

<https://catalogo.uffizi.it/it/viewer/#/main/viewer?idMetadato=1180045&type=iccd>

8, Heinrich Aldegrever, *Expulsion from Paradise*, 1540. National Gallery of Art, Washington, DC. Available from:

<https://www.nga.gov/artworks/3431-expulsion-paradise>

9, Rembrandt van Rijn, *Adam and Eve*, 1638. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam. Available from:

<https://www.rijksmuseum.nl/en/collection/object/Adam-and-Eve-a7a9bcb1ca37c117edf8dc0ccdb779a3>

10, Heinrich Aldegrever, *Adam with a Bear*, 1529. The Met, OA.

11, Lucas Cranach the Elder, *Adam and Eve*, ca. 1538. National Gallery, Prague - Collection of Old Masters. Available from:

https://sbirky.ngprague.cz/en/dielo/CZE:NG.DO_5380

Figure 5. The umbilical “serpent”.

In certain depictions of original sin, Adam’s umbilicus is veiled by the petiole of a leaf. Here, by contrast, Eve’s navel – turned toward the serpent – takes on the semblance of an eye (Image 1), as if beckoning us to see that creature as the umbilical cord. Is it to invite such a reading that Lucas Cranach the Elder, not content with painting navels on Adam and Eve (who, in principle, should have none, having not been born), endowed the serpent itself – a reptile naturally bereft of such a mark – with a navel (Image 2)? A

comparison between Cranach's serpent and a modern photograph of a placenta and umbilical cord (Image 3) strengthens the resemblance between the serpent and the cord. Moreover, in *The Fountain of Youth* (Image 5), Cranach portrays young bathers whose visages mirror his serpent's, as if conjuring the biblical creature bathing in amniotic waters.

To further affirm the serpent's meaning as the umbilical cord, once attached to the belly, one need only recall God's pronouncement: "upon your belly you shall go" (Genesis 3:14; Image 4).

Images:

1, Berthold Furtmeyr (or another member of his school of illuminators), *Eve and the Serpent*, between 1465 and 1470. Illumination on folio 10r of the *Furtmeyr-Bibel (Deutsche Bibel AT, Genesis - Ruth)*. Bavarian State Library (BSB), Munich. Bayerische Staatsbibliothek München - BSB Cgm 8010 a, fol. 10r, [urn:nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00045292-3](https://nbn:de:bvb:12-bsb00045292-3). PDM 1.0.

<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/>

2, Lucas Cranach the Elder, *Paradies [The Garden of Eden]*, 1530, detail. Staatliche Kunstsammlungen Dresden, Gemäldegalerie Alte Meister (Dresden State Art Collections, Old Masters Picture Gallery), Dresden, Germany. Photo Credit: bpk / Staatliche Kunstsammlungen Dresden / Hans-Peter Klut.

3, *Placenta with cord*. Photo: “Inferis”, Wikimedia Commons, CC BY-SA 2.0. Reproduced under the same licence.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/>

4, Johann Sadeler the Elder, *Expulsion from Paradise*, 1643. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

5, Lucas Cranach the Elder, *Der Jungbrunnen [The Fountain of Youth]*, 1546, detail. Gemäldegalerie, National Museums in Berlin. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

Figure 6. Hidden Symbolism in Medieval and Renaissance Art.

In Image 1, the stem-cavities – all except that of the apple in the serpent’s mouth – face left, mirroring the direction of Adam and Eve’s navels, while the blossom-cavities, positioned at the base of the apples where the flowers once bloomed, point to the right. In Image 2, the orientation is reversed: the stem-cavities face right, aligning with the placement of the navels, while the blossom-cavities face left, aligning with the placement of the anuses. In the ivory jewel of Image 3, the infant Jesus cradles an apple beside his belly in the left panel, while in the right, the fruit appears poised upon the navel of the crucified.

Images:

1, Albrecht Dürer, *The Fall of Man* (from the *The Small Passion* series), ca. 1510. The Met, OA.

2, Albrecht Dürer, *The Expulsion from Paradise* (from *The Small Passion* series), 1510. The Met, OA.

3, Unknown French artist, *Diptych with the Coronation of the Virgin and the Crucifixion*, ca. 1340–60. The Met, OA.

Figure 7. Byzantine Symbolism.

Whereas bodybuilders may exhibit striations beside the navel that faintly recall the spread wings of a bird, this depiction, defying any known human anatomy, presents Adam with a form encircling his navel that astonishingly resembles an apple.

Image:

Unknown Byzantine artist, *God Confronts Adam and Eve*, 12th–13th century. Mosaic in the Cathedral of the Assumption,

Monreale, Palermo, Sicily. Photograph taken by Richard Stracke, shared on <https://christianiconography.info/> under Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike licence. Reproduced here under the same licence. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/3.0/>

The terrestrial paradise — I emphasise: the terrestrial, not the celestial — represents the womb. In Image 1, Adam and Eve bend down to pass through the low gate of Paradise as they depart at the moment of their expulsion: the lowness and narrowness of this portal seems to suggest the exit from the maternal genital tract. In Image 2, Paradise appears as a pear-shaped space with a door, evoking the womb and simultaneously echoing both an enclosed domain and the uterine wall. In Image 3, the area from which a blinding light descends upon Eden at the moment of man's creation also bears a shape reminiscent of the human abdomen, and the position of the man's head corresponds strikingly to that of the navel, centrally located on the lower belly.

Images:

1, Unknown English artist, *The Transgression and Expulsion*, ca. 1337-1340. Miniature on folio 4r of *The Holkham Bible Picture Book*. British Library, London. Ms. Add. 47682. Image from *The Public Domain Review* [Internet; cited 4 August 2025]. Available from:

<https://pdimagearchive.org/images/bde572e6-4441-46ed-b69e-e654d04f1ac0/>

2, Edward Goodall, *The Expulsion from Paradise*, 1835. Title-page Vignette to Milton's *Paradise Lost*, Book XI. After Joseph Mallord William Turner. Yale Centre for British Art, Paul Mellon Collection, B1977.14.13733. Image Courtesy of the Centre; released into the public domain under CC0 1.0.

<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

3, Johann Elias Ridinger, *A Blinding Light Descends on Eden in the Creation of Man and the Animals*, ca. 1750. Wellcome Collection, London. Source: Wellcome Collection. Public Domain Mark. <https://creativecommons.org/public-domain/pdm/>

Figure 9. The Dance of the Apple.

The serpent and Eve seduced Adam with an apple (Image 3); the oriental dancer undulates like a “serpent” and seduces men with her belly (Images 1, 2, 7). Most often, the dancer’s navel remains the sole intimate part exposed. In Image 2, the entire belly lies bare while almost all the rest of the body is veiled. At other times the navel is concealed – if only by a small ornament (Image 7) – even when all other *pudenda* are bared (Images 10 and 11), exuding its enigmatic allure as the most sexually charged part of the female body. Yet the dancer can be entirely draped, revealing only her face, hands, feet, and, on occasion, her throat (Image 4). In Image 5, where all *pudenda* are veiled, the belly is bare save for the band at the navel’s height, the navel itself being consciously treated as *pudendum*.

I am uncertain whether Harem dancers revealed their midriffs during performances; perhaps their navels were as covered as that of the desert dancer in Image 6. I recall, as a child, watching women dance in attire that was somewhat similar to this one. They wore a stole wrapped tightly around their waist, covering

their navel even though it was already concealed by their dress; or draped around their hips. One end of the stole, tied at the hip, hung loosely over their thigh, as if symbolising the umbilical cord. The ‘*almeh*’ is far more than a seductress – mother, just as the “navel” of the forbidden apple is more than a sexual symbol.

Images:

1, Jean-Léon Gérôme, *The Almeh with Pipe*, 1871. Location unknown to the author. PDI from WikiArt.

2, Alfred Henri Darjou, *Dance in a Café by the Nile*, 1869, detail. Location unknown to the author. This image, along with Image 5, is drawn from Onok-art, “Belly Dance”, by Kasim [Internet; cited 21 January 2025]. Available from:

<https://onokart.wordpress.com/2010/11/02/belly-dance/>

3, Claude Monet, *Apples and Grapes*, 1880, detail. The Art Institute of Chicago. Image made available by the Institute under Creative Commons Zero (CC0) Public Domain Designation, abbreviated below as “AIC, CC0”.

4, Frédéric Auguste Antoine Goupil-Fesquet, *Almeh du Caire* (*Almeh of Cairo*). Image from *Voyage d’Horace Vernet en Orient*

[*Journey of Horace Vernet to the Orient*] written by Mr Goupil-Fesquet: Paris, Challamel, 1843. Reproduced with the kind permission of the Aikaterini Laskaridis Foundation, Hellenic Library - Alexander S. Onassis Public Benefit Foundation, Piraeus, Greece.

5, Leopold Carl Müller, *An Almée's Admirers*, 1882, detail. Location unknown to the author. Onok-art.

6, Otto Pilny, *Dance in the Desert*, 1913, detail. Private collection; location unknown to the author. PDI from Artvee.

7, Hans Zatzka, *Harem Entertainers*, undated (late 19th or first half of 20th century), detail. Private collection; location unknown to the author. PDI from WikiArt. Like many other painters, Zatzka did not depict the navel in its precise anatomical position but placed it slightly lower than the midpoint of the abdomen; I confirmed the navel's position in this painting by comparing it to both its placement in other works by the same artist and its actual anatomical location.

8, Hans Zatzka, *An Oriental Beauty with Roses*, undated (late 19th or first half of 20th century). Private collection; location unknown to the author. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

9, Otto Pilny, *A Dance at Sunset*, undated (late 19th or first half of 20th century), detail. Unknown location. PDI from Artvee.

10, Hans Zatzka, *Dancing Beauty*, undated (late 19th or first half of 20th century). Location unknown to the author. Available from Onok-art, “Belly Dance”, by Kasim [Internet; cited 10 August 2025] at:

<https://onokart.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2010/11/hans-zatzka-austrian-painter-1859-1945-dancing-beauty.jpg>

11, Hans Zatzka, *The Odalisque*, undated (late 19th or first half of 20th century). Location unknown to the author. Available from Wikimedia Commons [Internet; cited 10 August 2025] at:

[https://commons.m.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:The Odalisque by Hans Zatzka.jpg](https://commons.m.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:The_Odalisque_by_Hans_Zatzka.jpg)

Figure 10. Salomé’s Dance of Death.

Was it a belly dance? This remains uncertain, at least with regard to the biblical Salomé (Matthew 14:1-12; Mark 6:14-29), rather than to Oscar Wilde’s version (1893). Nevertheless, in all forms of Oriental dance, the female body undulates “like a serpent”, as illustrated in Image 1 with the serpent coiled around Salomé’s arm above the severed head of John the Baptist. In Image 2, shadows on the executioner’s garment form the illusion of a large, navel-like indentation on his abdomen, beside the Baptist’s head – soon to be severed at the level of the “Adam’s apple”.

Images:

1, Gustave Moreau (or after him), *Salomé Dancing Before the Head of St. John the Baptist*, mid to late 19th century. The Met, OA.

2, Benozzo Gozzoli, *The Feast of Herod and the Beheading of Saint John the Baptist*, ca. 1461-1462. NGA, OA.

Figure 11. Mother's Orchard.

In Image 1, a young boy enjoys an apple his mother has picked. His navel is not distinctly visible, perhaps because he has not yet finished eating the fruit. In Image 2, the “god of love” does not bestow an apple upon Venus for one of her lovers, but instead receives apples from his mother. In these depictions, as also in Image 4, the fruit passes not from woman to man but from mother to son, intimating that the representations of original sin portray not only the first man with his wife offering him the apple of sexuality, but, at a deeper level, the first son, Cain, with “the mother of all living” (Genesis 3:20) offering him the apple of bodily existence.

Image 4 portrays a child raising a basket of apples above his head, his arms extended like a crucifix, thus embodying the “bearer of the world’s sins”, Jesus of Nazareth. His arched body, curving backward, reveals a navel reminiscent of an apple. Here, the artist seeks to convey the connection between labour and the earth: the child partakes in the process of making apple cider, symbolising both work and the perpetuity of life. This image also reflects on the relationship between “sin” and labour as penance:

“By the sweat of your face you shall eat bread until you return to the ground” (Genesis 3:19). Nevertheless, when labour is undertaken with love – when the earth is cherished – can work truly be viewed as penance? No more than a man who loves a woman and loves to procreate would deem intimacy sinful, or a woman who reveres motherhood would regard the *travail* of childbirth as a punishment.

Hence, in Images 1, 2 and 4, the apple becomes a symbol of dignity, akin to the ancient *‘awālim* who, before being reduced to mere courtesans in perception, represented knowledge, virtue, respectability – motherhood. Likewise, in the narrative of the Fall, the forbidden fruit transcends a merely sexual interpretation: it embodies maternal nourishment, its stem-cavity poignantly evoking the child’s separation from the mother, as suggested by Image 5, where Cain already appears beside Adam and Eve in their expulsion from Paradise.

Images:

1, Pierre Cécile Puvis De Chavannes, *Récolte des Pommes [Apple picking]*, ca. 1890. Renwick Gallery of the Smithsonian American

Art Museum, Washington, DC. Image made available by the Smithsonian Institution under the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) licence.

2, Hans Zatzka, *Sweet Apple*, unknown date (late 19th or first half of 20th century). Private collection; location unknown to the author. PDI.

3, Pierre-Auguste Renoir, *Pears and Apples*, 1890, detail. Location unknown to the author. PDI from WikiArt.

4, Pierre Puvis de Chavannes, *Cider*, ca. 1864, detail. The Met, OA.

5, Lucas van Leyden, *The Expulsion from Paradise*, 1510. Philadelphia Museum of Art. PDI from the Museum's website.

6, Carl Schuch, *Still Life with Apples, Pears and a Carafe*, ca. 1888, detail. Städel Museum, Frankfurt am Main.

7, Jan van Eyck, *Portrait of Giovanni(?) Arnolfini and his Wife*, 1434. The National Gallery, London. Available from:

<https://www.nationalgallery.org.uk/paintings/jan-van-eyck-the-arnolfini-portrait>

8, Hubert and Jan van Eyck, *The Ghent Altarpiece: Eve* (outermost right panel of the upper register of the opened polyptych), between 1425 and 1432. Saint Bavo's Cathedral, Ghent, Belgium. Available from:

<https://artsandculture.google.com/asset/the-ghent-altarpiece-eve-hubert-and-jan-van-eyck/PgHrGpXCNcy2ig?hl=en>

Figure 12. The Cord of Sin: The Apple as a Symbol of Embryonic Sustenance.

Though the serpent forms a composite figure — embodying both the penis and the umbilical cord — these concealed meanings, united in a single figure, remain distinct in their allegiances: as a penis, the serpent pertains in the narrative solely to Adam; as an organ bound to Cain, it takes on the role of the umbilical cord.

In Images 3 and 4, as in many other depictions of original sin, Eve, in contradiction to Genesis 3:6, has already given, or is in the act of giving, an apple to Adam before taking her own from the tree or from the serpent. This may be understood in two complementary ways: first, as a *dénégation* of the fact that offering the apple signifies nourishment through the umbilical cord — an act the woman cannot perform without first “eating” the apple herself, that is, becoming pregnant; and second, as a figure of seduction, in which the gift becomes the offering of her belly — together with other rounded forms — to be “consumed” by the man’s gaze.

In Image 2, unless she has already eaten hers, Eve appears to be taking the first apple from the serpent; yet one might wonder whether she is truly receiving the apple or instead placing it into

the serpent's mouth: the positioning of her hand leaves room for doubt as to the apple's trajectory. In Image 1, however, the placement of her fingers, the expression of her lips, and the fact that she already holds an apple in her left hand, lend a reasonable degree of certainty to the interpretation that Eve is actively placing the apple into the mouth of the serpent. This serpent, into whose "mouth" Eve is inserting the fruit, symbolises the umbilical cord through which she nourishes her embryo. Simultaneously, the serpent from whose mouth she previously received the fruit represents the phallus of her husband. This reading aligns with Genesis 3:6, where the woman eats first and then gives "some" to another — who, in this context, is not her husband but the embryo conceived with her husband. The word "some" suggests that she and the other person partook of the same apple, aligning with the notion that the other person represents the embryo, nourished by the very food consumed by its mother — an idea illustrated quite clearly in Image 3, where the woman plucks an apple with one hand while simultaneously extending another in offering with the other.

On the left-hand door of St Mary's Cathedral in Hildesheim, Germany (Figure 16.7, p. 134), Eve appears to have already begun eating her apple while simultaneously handing a fruit to the man. The representation of the shared nourishment between mother and embryo is rendered even more strikingly in a relief at the entrance to Notre Dame Cathedral in Paris (Image 5), where Eve eats from the fruit while, at the very same moment, offering the apple to Adam or Cain through their arms, outstretched between their bellies like a cord that connects them. A similar representation appears in Image 11, where the hands meet before the serpent, and the navels are clearly visible. Yet the most powerful image of umbilical nourishment in the context of the Adam and Eve narrative is found in the pre-Gothic Salerno Ivories (Image 7). In this depiction, Eve eats with one hand while giving with the other, and the other person receives with one hand while eating with the other. But why does Eve give simultaneously both to the man's hand and to her mouth? And why does the positioning of the supposed man's right hand resemble that of another person's hand, facing the man? This positioning suggests

that the right hand of the man is not his own but rather that of the woman, who is simultaneously eating with her left hand and placing the apple into the mouth of the man with her right. Is this interaction a kiss between a woman and a man, or does it symbolise the umbilical connection between a woman and her embryo? If the primary point of connection is the lips, what then is the meaning of the connection between the woman's right hand and the man's left? The improbable conjunction of two points of connection – hands giving and receiving before the bellies, and hands eating and feeding the other person's mouth – suggests that the true point of connection lies neither in the hands nor the lips, but rather in the navel.

Another compelling argument in favor of this interpretation lies in the texture of the fruit held in the hands of Adam and Eve in Image 7: it is not rigid like an apple or any conventional fruit – except, maybe, a fig – but malleable, more akin to dough. This flexibility evokes the umbilical cord (see also Figure 16.3, p. 134). Furthermore, this flexibility evokes the association of bread with the placenta – a term first introduced by Realdo Colombo to

describe the organ of pregnancy, owing to its resemblance to a “flat cake” (Klein, 1971, p. 565; Pizzi et al., 2012, Fig. 2) — a connection that underlies the tradition of baking cakes for birthdays. This imagery is further enriched by an Armenian depiction of the *shared meal* (Image 8), where the bread, delicately held between the fingers of Christ, features a depression reminiscent of a navel or of an apple stem-cavity.

Eve, the woman, seduces Adam, not with a literal apple as an “aphrodisiac”, but with the sight of her apple-shaped belly. From this angle, the sexual “serpent” through which Eve received the “fruit” becomes Adam’s penis, aroused by the visual feast of her body. In the context of the girl’s Oedipus complex, this evokes a conflation of the umbilical cord that once linked her to her mother with the husband’s penis. Yet the serpent from which the daughter, like the son, receives the fruit is not sexual; it signifies the umbilical cord, and the person to whom Eve truly gave the fruit — as the symbol of his own body, to “eat”, not merely to behold or to penetrate — was Cain, not Adam; the latter “ate” her body only with his eyes. This act of visual consumption is vividly depicted in

Image 9, where Adam appears to eat the apple first, then takes another from the serpent to offer to Eve. The man beholds – and absorbs visually – the seductive belly and other rounded forms, before offering her, through his erected serpent-penis, the apple-embryo.

Notably, in Image 3, the colour of the serpent matches the hue of Eve’s right arm, signifying that the serpent, as a representation of Cain’s umbilical cord, is an extension of Eve’s body. Were Adam’s phallus also visible in this depiction, the artist would likely have rendered it in the same colour, emphasizing the conceptual link between the snake, the penis of Adam, and the umbilical cord between the invisible Cain and Eve. See also Image 12 which “imagines Eve’s accepting the forbidden fruit [probably hers] from the serpent as happening simultaneously with Adam’s [receiving it from Eve with his left hand and] eating it [with his right]” (Faletra, n.d.). In this depiction – and even more clearly in Image 8 of Figure 13 (pp. 103–121), where the serpent is shown between Adam and Eve – the woman is not portrayed as eating the fruit; perhaps she has already partaken of it and is now passing

a portion, through the serpent, to “Adam”-Cain, who is depicted receiving it with one hand while simultaneously consuming a fruit with the other — a simultaneity that suggests the apple’s passage from Eve to the other’s organ of consumption occurred through a physical connector in which receiving and consuming are one and the same: the umbilical cord (Figures 13-15, pp. 103-133).

Different moments are condensed into a single image — much like in a dream — reflecting a common approach in many depictions of original sin; yet the condensation also *fuses* Adam with Cain. If a depiction unites Adam’s receiving of the fruit with one hand and his eating with the other, it may signify that the figure is not simply Adam, but Cain — receiving not with the hand and eating not with the mouth, but with the navel through the umbilical cord. In Figure 13.20 (see the reference on page 119), as in Image 3, Eve is depicted handing a fruit to Adam, who already holds one. This gesture may be interpreted as the offering of two apples — one to the father, the other to the son fused with the father. Such a reading is particularly compelling in Image 3, where it is less plausible to see a condensation of two successive moments in the

act of sinning: Adam uses his right hand solely to hold an apple, neither to eat nor to receive, while Eve appears to offer him a fruit to the very hand in which he already holds one – as in Image 12 and similar depictions, where she seems to present the apple to the hand with which he is *not eating*. By contrast, in Figure 13.20, a condensation of the acts of receiving and eating is more admissible – not only because Eve offers an apple to the same hand with which Adam already holds a fruit (a gesture still compatible with the notion of receiving a *second, different* apple with the same hand), but also because the constraints of pictorial representation preclude depicting a single hand both receiving and consuming. See also Figures 16.1, 3, 6 and most strikingly 16.7 (p. 134), where Adam holds one apple in his right hand while extending the other to receive the same (condensation of successive moments in Adam’s sin) or a second one (condensation of the figures of Adam and Cain: that is, fusion father-son).

Perhaps the most suggestive condensation of different *moments* in the act of sinning – that is, separation between the figures of Adam and the future Cain – appears in Image 10: the

man eats a fruit — seemingly a pear or fig — while the woman consumes hers and simultaneously holds a third, not offering it to him but cradling it near her belly, as if keeping it for the unborn — a future being distinct from the father. A similar triadic symbolism, where a condensation is more admissible than a fusion, recurs in Figure 16.10 (p. 141): Adam holds one apple in his left hand while appearing to receive — or indeed to give — a second, larger one — representing the belly of the pregnant woman — with his right; Eve, meanwhile, holds a third, smaller apple — symbolising the embryo — close to her own belly. The apple given to the son represents his very body, not merely sexual desire — it symbolises his corporeal existence.

It is worth noting that, in Figure 16.7 (p. 134), although the condensation seems less a fusion of distinct stages in Adam's sin in a single image than a conflation of Adam with Cain, the alternating use of right and left arms from Eve to Adam nonetheless suggests an interpretation in which multiple temporalities are enfolded within a single image. At the same time, this alternation may subtly evoke the uninterrupted umbilical

trajectory linking Eve to Cain. The image is thus ambiguous: there is a trace of Cain in Adam, just as there is a shadow of Adam in Cain. My aim, however, is to disentangle the two figures as far as possible – even if a complete separation remains an unattainable ideal.

Yesterday, someone asked me why I am so concerned with distinguishing Adam from Cain. The answer is simple: because *they* conflate the two by confusing sex with birth, insisting that the apple is a symbol of sexuality, when in truth it obviously signifies, above all, the navel. In causing God the “Father” to overlook him who loved the “fruits” of the earth, this confusion consigned the firstborn to the fate of a transgressor. Isn’t it time to prevent excessive guilt – both Oedipal guilt and the guilt of being born – from turning us into “pale criminals” (Nietzsche, 1883–85, pp. 36–39)?

Images:

1, Albrecht Dürer, *Adam and Eve*, 1504. The Met, OA.

2, Albrecht Dürer, *The Fall of Man* (part of *The Small Passion* series), ca. 1510. The Met, OA.

3, Jan Saenredam, *Zondeval [Fall of Man]*, 1604. After design by Abraham Bloemaert. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

4, Lucas Cranach the Elder, *The Fall of Man*, 1509. AIC, CC0.

5, Part of the pedestal of the *Madonna and Child* statue adorning the western portal of Notre-Dame de Paris, France, 12th-13th century CE. Retouched picture by Jebulon / Creative Commons, CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication.

6, Johann Sadeler, *Adam en Eva verbergen zich voor God de Vader [Adam and Eve hide from God the Father]*, 1643, detail. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

7, Unknown artist, *Tentazione e peccato originale [Temptation and Original Sin]*, ca. 1084 CE. Right panel of a relief ivory tablet from the Cathedral of Salerno. Museo del Duomo, Salerno, Italy. Photo © Peter (petrus.agricola) on Flickr. Attempts were made to contact the copyright holder for permission to reproduce the image, but no response was received. Given the scientific and educational purpose of this publication, and in the absence of an available alternative, the image is included with full attribution.

8, Daniel of Uranc, *Feeding the Multitude*, 1433. Illumination on parchment from the Gospel of the Armenian medieval artist. Mesrop Mashtots Research Institute of Ancient Manuscripts, Yerevan. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

9, Unknown 13th-century miniaturist, *Psalterium non feriatum [Weekday Psalter]* - Cod. Lichtenthal 25, fol. 46r. Oberrhein, [2. Hälfte des 13. Jh.]. Karlsruhe : Badische Landesbibliothek, 2013. [Internet; cited 10 February 2025]. The image remains unaltered aside from cropping and its incorporation into a collage. Available from:

<https://digital.blb->

[karlsruhe.de/blbhs/Handschriften/content/pageview/1190600](https://digital.blb-)

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10, Unknown artist, *Original Sin*, ca. 1300–1325. Illumination in the *Maastricht Hours*, Netherlands (Liège). From the British Library Collection: Stowe MS 17, fol. 26v. Reproduced with kind permission.

11, Unknown artist, *Original Sin*, ca. 1220-1230. Relief on the right portal of the west façade of Amiens Cathedral, France. Image available in Cummings, 2020.

12, Unknown English artist, *Original Sin*, ca. 1123-1143. Illumination from the *St Alban's Psalter*. Dombibliothek Hildesheim, MS St God. 1 (Property of the Basilika of St Godehard, Hildesheim). Image available from Falettra (n.d.).

Figure 13. Physical “temptation”.

The role of the serpent-cord as a physical link between Adam and Eve – rather than merely an intermediary “tempter” – appears

subtly in these and many other depictions of original sin where Adam and Eve stand on either side of the tree, one to the left, the other to the right, their hands reaching out to meet just before the serpent's body with which — or with the trunk-umbilical-cord of the tree of the knowledge, merging itself with the serpent as singularly seen in Images 5 and 28 — they seem to merge (see other images in Cummings, 2020a; 2020b further notes that, by the 12th century, the depiction of “Adam and Eve on either side of the serpent-entwined Tree of Knowledge” had become the dominant ecclesiastical representation of original sin).

The fusion of serpent and trunk is rendered with a particular force in Image 5, though there the serpent appears more as a phallus penetrating the tree than merging with it. This fusion appears most clearly in Image 28, where a digital artist's unconscious vividly conceived the serpent of temptation and the trunk of the tree of the knowledge as one and the same.

In Image 4, the role of physical connector is suggested by the fact that Adam — though receiving the fruit from Eve at some distance from the serpent's body — strangely places his left hand

upon the serpent coiled around the tree, while taking the fruit with the other. Furthermore, several dark spots on this wooden ceiling of St. Michael's Church in Germany appear to result from nails driven into the ends of each wooden plank. Yet it is striking that these marks are concentrated almost exclusively on the bodies of Adam and Eve, with very few outside this area — prompting the question of whether the painter deliberately positioned the figures to align with the dark points, while surrounding them with an abundance of fruit. Mirroring the multitude of dark marks resembling navels, the profusion of fruit — not borne by the tree — surrounding the pair may suggest a symbolic parallel: just as the numerous dark marks resemble many navels on the bodies of Adam and Eve, so too do the many fruits symbolise navels. Even if the artist did not consciously choose to place the figures on this precise section of the wood, it is possible that, upon noticing the dark, navel-like spots where he had drawn them, he may have been unconsciously led to add a corresponding abundance of fruit in the background — thus subtly inviting us to see the forbidden fruit as a symbol of the navel.

Strikingly, a stylised depiction of the heart encircles Eve’s navel in Image 2, eloquently substantiating my interpretation that the so-called “apple” of love and sexuality is, in truth, the belly itself – as further evidenced by a rare artistic representation in which the god of Love is associated with a serpent and portrayed with an exceptionally pronounced navel (Image 26).

In another section of the nave wall depicting the Genesis story at Monreale Cathedral, a shape distinctly resembling an apple encircles Adam’s navel (Image 15), powerfully reinforcing the notion that the heart around Eve’s navel in Image 2 represents none other than the forbidden fruit.

The umbilical significance of the relationship between sex and love – both symbolised by the heart-apple – and the navel is eloquently illustrated in Image 29, where the umbilical cord, here symbolised not merely by the fruit’s peduncle but by the trunk of the tree of the knowledge itself, emerges from the concavity at the top of the stylized heart, which resembles the navel. This drawing was created for a birth certificate, in which the heart symbolises the child – the “fruit” of the union between man and woman – further

supporting the idea that the trunk-serpent, connected to the heart's "stem-cavity", represents the umbilical cord.

In his foxed rendering of the Fall of Man (Figure 4.1, p. 61), Lucas van Leyden depicts Adam receiving the apple with one hand, while his other curiously grasps a protruding part of the tree – an ambiguous form that strikingly evokes either a phallic shape or an umbilical cord. Here, in Image 10, Adam does not grasp the low-hanging branch; instead, the apple offered by Eve and received by Adam aligns precisely with the section of the serpent's body that curves behind the tree – just as Eve's hand does in Image 16 and other similar depictions.

Van Leyden's drawing bears a further large brownish stain between the apple and the rounded bulge of the tree trunk, itself centred on a dark cavity that vividly evokes a navel – as if to accentuate that the hollow constitutes the apple's most significant feature. Also note the cord-like elongation descending from beneath the apple-like bulge.

Although hollowed bulges are common on apple tree trunks, particularly in older specimens, it is perhaps not by mere chance

that several artists depicted belly-shaped swellings in strategically prominent positions on the trunk of the tree of the knowledge – such as the distinct bulges between the faces of Adam and Eve in Images 7 and 17, the rounded protrusion on the trunk in Figure 16.6 (p. 134), or the large, navel-shaped hollow on the trunk in Image 18, positioned directly between the navels and curiously resembling a large mammal’s nostril – an organ of aerial respiration.

In Image 23, two hollowed bulges distinctly overlap the body of the serpent entwined around the trunk of the tree of the knowledge, lending further support to my interpretation that the serpent in Genesis symbolises the umbilical cord, as likewise suggested by the figure of an ivory serpent, freshly created by God, coiling around an aerial cord and outlining black hollows that recall the navel (Image 24).

In Image 12, a thick branch emerges from the lower part of the trunk, jutting out beneath the others, and appears almost indistinguishable from the serpent’s body – supporting the interpretation that the tree of the knowledge symbolises the

placenta, with its trunk representing the umbilical cord. The latter is not a sexual organ, neither masculine nor feminine; yet, as it forms within the female body, femininity is more closely associated with the serpent than masculinity. This association is reflected in numerous depictions where the woman's arm alone overlaps the serpent and/or the trunk (Image 25), or where her arm is more closely aligned with the serpent's body than the man's – as seen in Images 1, 8, 19, 20 and 21. In Image 20, Eve's right arm is painted the same colour as the adjacent section of the tree trunk with which it overlaps. In Image 21, the hand of Eve and that of the serpent are positioned in such symmetrical opposition as to suggest a visual – and almost anatomical – continuity between their bodies.

Tellingly, the prominently rounded belly and corded girdle of the woman tempting Saint Anthony in the desert (Image 11) may well dispel any lingering doubt about the serpent's latent identity in the Fall narrative. No less telling is the bride's distended belly – and the fruits, those age-old emblems of fertility whose significance hardly requires comment – in *The Arnolfini Portrait* (Figure 11.7; see the reference on page 87).

In Image 9, Eve grasps a branch of the tree with her right hand while offering a fruit to Adam with her left, as if to suggest that her left arm represents the trunk of her placental tree, and she is seated on a broken branch, as if to suggest that this branch represents the umbilical cord — one that shall be severed once the fruit is received by Adam/Cain.

One might well wonder why, unlike in other depictions where Adam's and Eve's hands are often apart yet near, in Image 3 their separated hands, along with the apple's largest portion, are depicted precisely before the empty segment where neither serpent nor tree trunk appears — at the very spot where the serpent gives the visual impression of being severed. Could this arrangement suggest that the apple's defining feature is its stem cavity, symbolising the severance of the cord? Note also that the apple's peduncle appears to emerge from the trunk rather than from a branch — albeit in a reversed orientation — further reinforcing the suggestion that the peduncle represents the trunk of the placental tree: the umbilical cord.

Moreover, in Image 21, where four red apples are depicted, the placement of the two central fruits relative to Adam's and Eve's fingers suggests not the literal presence of multiple apples, but rather a temporal condensation. Eve appears to be casting the fruit toward Adam. The motion is rendered with subtlety: the apple is shown twice within the same frame — first, still in contact with Eve's outstretched fingers, and then, slightly farther along its trajectory, just as it nears Adam's hand. Suspended in mid-air, the fruit traverses the space between them, passing visibly in front of the serpent's coiled body as it winds around the tree trunk. This condensation — more precisely, a clear temporal layering — allows us to witness both the act of giving and the imminent reception. Yet the composition, in which the apple crosses the air between Adam and Eve, also seems to underscore that the punishment of Original Sin is the severing of the cord and the beginning of aerial respiration.

In image 14, the tree of the knowledge is not positioned centrally between Adam and Eve; however, the serpent's arm fuses with Eve's, and its form is so entangled with the tree that what

appears to be its arms becomes indistinguishable from the branches – one of which Adam grasps, as though to receive the apple from Eve’s branch through the mediation of the placental tree.

In Image 6, the two hands and the apple are vertically aligned, one above the other, parallel to the trunk of the tree of the knowledge – as if to clearly show that the trunk symbolises the umbilical cord through which the “apple”, that is, the body, is transmitted from mother to embryo.

In Image 22, the serpent’s function as a physical link between Adam and Eve is rendered with striking clarity: their fully outstretched arms converge precisely at the level of the serpent’s body, making it the literal and visual point of transmission between them – an arrangement more explicit than in most other depictions.

In Image 13, Adam’s and Eve’s hands are markedly distant from one another – a visual reflection of the idea that the punishment of Original Sin is the severing of the cord. Also noteworthy is the depiction of the diabolical creature with wings

that beat the air. This further reinforces the association of aerial respiration with the satanic, as breath is bound up with death – and it calls to mind those sombre lines:

« Ainsi qu'un débauché pauvre qui baise
et mange
Le sein martyrisé d'une antique catin,
Nous volons au passage un plaisir
clandestin
Que nous pressons bien fort comme une
vieille orange.

Dans nos cerveaux malsains, comme un
million d'helminthes,
Grouille, chante et ripaille un peuple de
Démons,
Et, quand nous respirons, la Mort dans
nos poumons
S'engouffre, comme un fleuve, avec de
sourdes plaintes. »

(Baudelaire, 1857a, p. 6.)

“Like a penniless rake who with kisses and
bites
Tortures the breast of an old prostitute,
We steal as we pass by a clandestine
pleasure
That we squeeze very hard like a dried up
orange.

Serried, swarming, like a million maggots,
A legion of Demons carouses in our
brains,
And when we breathe, Death, that unseen
river,
Descends into our lungs with muffled
wails.”

(Baudelaire, 1857b, pp. 3-4, Aggeler W,
translator, 1954.)

It is true that the tree trunk is often too thick and insufficiently sinuous or serpentine to evoke an umbilical cord – yet, on one hand, the trunk readily condenses into its branches, and on the other, there exist trunks possessing a serpentine form. Is Christ's comparison of himself to the vine (John 15.1) solely due to the crimson hue of wine, redolent of blood? After all, other red fruit wines – cherry, pomegranate, blackberry – rival the grape in their rich, sanguine depths. Might Christ's comparison to the vine

transcend mere colour, arising instead from the vine's distinctive trunk, which twists and coils like a serpent or umbilical cord (as illustrated in Image 27), thereby adding a profound symbolism that invites contemplation?...

Image 27 is somewhat stylised and does not fully capture the complexity of a natural vine, featuring only a single peduncle, emerging directly from the branch, and one grape. Yet, this minimalism serves to prioritise conceptual clarity over botanical realism, emphasising the symbolic parallel between the trunk and the umbilical cord, as the unbranched trunk and lone grape clearly evoke the idea of a singular embryo connected to the placenta. Although each grape contains multiple seeds, it is botanically a single fruit and here symbolically represents a singular embryo connected to its mother.

Certainly, the trunk of the tree of the knowledge can represent the umbilical cord: with nearly the same force as in Image 28, the author of Image 30 depicted, by the *water*, the trunk of an apple tree with a curvature akin to that of an umbilical cord.

Images:

1, Lorenzo Maitani (probably by), *Original Sin*, ca. 1310. Marble relief on the façade of the Orvieto Cathedral, Italy. Photo: Luca Aless (CC BY-SA 4.0). Reproduced under the same licence.

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2, Unknown Byzantine artist, *Adam, Serpent and Eve*, ca. 1180. Mosaic in the Monreale Cathedral, Palermo, Sicily. Photo: Holger Uwe Schmitt (CC BY-SA 4.0). Reproduced under the same licence.

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3, Henry Styleman L'Estrange, *The Fall of Man*, ca. 1858, detail. Second panel of the nave ceiling at Ely Cathedral, Cambridgeshire, England. Image used with kind permission of Hirst Conservation Ltd. Available from:

<https://www.hirst-conservation.com/portfolio/nave-ceiling-ely-cathedral/>

4, Unknown Romanesque artist, *Original Sin*, ca. 1225–1250. Wooden ceiling of St. Michaelis Church of Hildesheim. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

5, Jacopo della Quercia, *Original Sin*, ca. 1425–1428. Relief on the portal of San Petronio, Bologna, Italy. Courtesy of Web Gallery of Art (<https://www.wga.hu/>). Reproduced with kind permission.

6, Lucas Cranach I, *Adam and Eve*, ca. 1528–1530, detail. Inv.no. 42, photo: Rik Klein Gotink, Royal Museum of Fine Arts Antwerp - Collection Flemish Community (public domain). Reproduced with kind permission.

7, Hendrick Goltzius, *Adam and Eve*, 1585. After Bartholomeus Spranger. The Met, OA.

8, Master of the Workshop of Blanche de Castille, *Original Sin*, ca. 1225–1235. Lower section of the illumination on folio 11v of the Psalter of Saint Louis and Blanche de Castille. Bibliothèque nationale de France (BnF), Paris, France. Bibliothèque de l’Arsenal. Ms-1186 réserve. Gallica, the BnF’s digital library, waives all fees for the commercial use of public-domain images in scholarly or academic publications; hereafter abbreviated as “Gallica scholarly”. Available from:

<https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b52508581r/f30.item>

9, Lucas van Leyden, *The Fall of Man*, ca. 1530. NGA, OA.

10, Augustin Hirschvogel, *Adam and Eve Eating the Forbidden Fruit* (from “Old and New Testaments”), 1548, detail. The Met, OA. Available from:

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/811592>

11, Lucas van Leyden, *The Temptation of St. Anthony*, 1509, detail. The Met, OA.

12, Lucas van Leyden, *De zondeval* [*The Fall of Man*], ca. 1512–1516. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

13, Maître François, detail from the illumination on folio 27r of Saint Augustin’s *La Cité de Dieu* [*The City of God*], translated into French by Raoul de Presles, ca. 1371–1375. BnF, Paris, France. Département des Manuscrits. Français 19. Gallica scholarly. Available from:

<https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b105325999/f57.item>

14, Michelangelo, *The Fall and Expulsion from Garden of Eden*, ca. 1509–1510. Part of the Sistine Chapel ceiling. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

15, Unknown Byzantine artist, *God Confronts Adam and Eve*, ca. 1180. Mosaic in the Monreale Cathedral, Palermo, Sicily. Photo: Richard Stracke (CC BY-NC-SA 3.0). Reproduced under the same licence.

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16, Giovanni Battista Leonetti, *The temptation of Adam* (plate XII from the series “Prints of the Duomo in Orvieto”), ca. 1791. After Nicolo Pisano. The British Museum, London. Available from:

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/P_1848-0205-490

17, Crispijn de Passe the Elder, *The Temptation of Adam and Eve*, ca. 1610. The British Museum, London. Available from:

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/P_1873-0809-702

18, Unknown artist, *Eve tempted by the serpent to eat the fruit of the Tree of Knowledge*, 17th century. Available from:

<https://www.bridgemanimages.com/en/european-school/eve-tempted-by-the-serpent-to-eat-the-fruit-of-the-tree-of-knowledge-engraving/engraving/asset/7172271?offline=1>

19, Anonymous, *Adam and Eve*, 1647. Sgraffito mural on the stone façade of the Clagluna House, Ardez, Engadine Valley, Switzerland. Available from:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Haus_Ardez1.JPG

20, Nicholas of Verdun, *The Fall*, 1181. Scene from the Verdun Altar in Klosterneuburg Abbey, Austria. Available from:

<https://archive.lesimgimages.com/photo/11765>

21, Anonymous English artist, *The Temptation of Adam and Eve*, ca. 1270–80. Miniature on folio 4r of *The Holland Psalter*. The Old Library of St John's College, University of Cambridge: MS K.26. Available from:

<https://www.pinterest.com/pin/46302702396810112/>

22, Unknown French artist, *The Fall from Grace*, ca. 1244–1254. Lower right scene from the illumination on folio 1v of the *Shah 'Abbas Bible*. The Morgan Library & Museum, New York. MS M.638. Available from:

<https://www.themorgan.org/collection/crusader-bible/2>

23, Unknown artist, *Sarcophagus of Agape and Crescentius*, ca. 325–350, detail. Museo Pio Cristiano, The Vatican. Photo:

Richard Stracke (CC BY-NC-SA 3.0). Reproduced under the same licence.

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24, Unknown Italian artist, *Plaque with God Creating the Animals*, 1084, detail. The Met, OA.

25, Masolino, *The Temptation of Adam and Eve*, 1425-1427. Brancacci Chapel, Florence. Available from:

http://www.museumsinflorence.com/musei/Brancacci_chapel.html

26, Antoine Bourdelle, *Eros au serpent* [*Eros with the Serpent*], 1923. Musée Bourdelle. Image placed in the public domain under a Creative Commons Ø licence (CCØ) by the Public Institution Paris Musées, hereafter abbreviated as « Paris Musées, CCØ ».

27, Image generated by AI.

28, Anonymus, *Tree of the Knowledge of Good and Evil with Snake*. Vector illustration purchased from iStock. Credit: FoxysGraphic.

29, Unknown artist and date (unavailable due to a technical error that prevented the author from reaching the source), *Birth*

Certificate for Maria Xander, German. From the Digital Collections of the Free Library of Philadelphia. Available from: <https://libwww.freelibrary.org/digital/item/6929>

30, Claude Monet, *Apple Trees in Blossom by the Water*, 1880.
Location unknown to the author. PDI from WikiArt.

Figure 14. Adam's Mother: Nature.

The role of the serpent as a physical link between Adam and Eve is also evident in the present Figure. Indeed, certain popular interpretations of the Fall closely associate Eve with the serpent – viewing her not merely as one who was tempted, but as the very embodiment of temptation and sin. In keeping with such readings, many artists have portrayed the serpent in the guise of a woman (Figures 5.1, 5.2, 8.1, 12.5, 12.10, 13.5, 13.13, 13.14, 14.1, 15.3, 16.1, 16.3, 18.5; see also numerous other depictions of original sin in Cummings, 2020a and Ahl, 2023). From this perspective, Eve and the serpent become interchangeable. Consequently, in Image 12, where Eve is depicted simultaneously taking the fruit from the serpent-woman (or from the tree) with one hand, and offering it to Adam with the other, the woman-serpent Eve functions quite literally as an umbilical conduit between Adam and the serpent-woman. Similarly, in Images 2-8, where Eve performs the same dual gesture – a movement reminiscent of the fluid choreography of belly dance, in which a woman often raises one arm as the other descends – this woman, conceived as a serpent,

once again serves as an umbilical bridge between male and female (see also Images 13-20 and several other depictions of original sin in Cummings, 2020a).

Other renderings of the Fall clearly associate Eve with the tree of the knowledge. In Image 9, the fact that the serpent is coiled around Eve does not only suggest that the woman, at least partly, is a serpent, as say misogynous people who still confound cord and penis, mother and woman, but also that Eve is the tree around which the serpent is coiled, as mature men would say.

Many depictions of original sin show Adam — or Cain — raising his hand to receive the fruit from Eve, who in turn raises hers to take it from the tree. These compositions suggest that Eve herself is the placental tree from which Cain takes the fruit. Interpreted as Adam, he receives it from the body-tree of Mother Nature. In Image 10, Adam takes the fruit not from Eve but directly from the tree — or from the serpent within it. In Image 11 and Figure 15.4 (p. 130), he does so even while simultaneously receiving a fruit from Eve. This dual gesture lends further support to the idea that, in other depictions, the tree symbolises the

placenta and Eve's body. Is Eve the mother? Then the man is Cain, drawing his body-fruit from the placental tree of Eve. Is she the sexual partner? Then he is Adam, drawing his body-fruit directly from Mother Nature, as in Images 10, 11 and Figures 15.2 and 15.4 (p. 130).

Images

1, Anonymous artist, *Original Sin*, 1522. Location unknown to the author. Image by www.BibleStudyMen.com, reproduced by kind permission of David Ahl.

2, Lucas van Leyden, *The Fall of Man*, 1529. NGA, OA.

3, Cornelis Galle the Elder, *Adam en Eva [Adam and Eve]*, ca. 1586-1612. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

4, Jean Massard, *Eve tempting Adam*, 1787. After Carlo Cignani. Wellcome Collection, London. Source: Wellcome Collection. Public Domain Mark.

5, Izaak van Oosten, *The Fall of Man*, between 1651 and 1662. Private Collection; location unknown to the author. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

6, Anonymous artist of the Italo-Flemish school, *Adam and Eve in the Garden of Eden*, 16th century. Location unknown to the author. Every reasonable effort was made to contact the copyright holder in order to obtain permission to reproduce this image; however, the author was unable to reach them. Given the scholarly and educational purpose of this publication, and in the absence of an alternative, the image is included with acknowledgement of the known source. Image available from:

<https://www.mutualart.com/Artwork/Adam-and-Eve-in-the-garden-of-Eden/3CCBFD049750CBEA>

7, Johann Sadeler I, *Eva verleidt Adam van de boom te eten* [*Eve tempts Adam to eat from the tree*], 1575. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

8, Gustave-Claude-Étienne Courtois, *Adam and Eve in the Earthly Paradise*, between 1902 and 1906. Location unknown to the author. Photo: Arnaud Clerget, Wikimedia Commons, CC BY-SA 3.0. Reproduced under the same licence.

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9, Franz von Stuck, *Adam and Eve*, ca. 1920. Städel Museum, Frankfurt am Main.

10, Adriaen Isenbrant, *Adam und Eva* [*Adam and Eve*], ca. 1520. Kunsthalle Bremen - The Kunstverein in Bremen, Germany. Photo: Lars Lohrisch, Public Domain Mark 1.0.

11, Frans Floris I, *The Fall of Man*, ca. 1560. Location unknown to the author. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

12, Leonaert Bramer, *Temptation of Adam and Eve*, 17th century. The British Museum, London. © The Trustees of the British Museum. Shared under a Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0) licence: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>

13, Circle of Joachim Antonisz Wtewael, *Adam and Eve in the Garden of Eden*, ca. late 16th-early 17th century. Private collection; location unknown to the author. Image available from:

<https://www.mutualart.com/Artwork/ADAM-AND-EVE-IN-THE-GARDEN-OF-EDEN/065145C45DA30EAA73F6CBB7433F9A9B>

14, Charles Joseph Natoire, *The Rebuke of Adam and Eve*, 1740.

Private collection; location unknown to the author. Image available from:

https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/d/de/Adam_and_Eve_before_the_Fall_by_Fran%C3%A7ois_Le_Moyne%2C_oil_on_copper.JPG

15, Clément Pierre Marillier, *Eve tombe, et fait tomber Adam* [*Eve Falls, and Causes Adam to Fall*], between 1789 and 1804.

Victoria and Albert Museum, London. Image available from:

<https://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O727852/eve-tombe-et-fait-tomber-print-cl%C3%A9ment-pierre-marillier/>

16, Cornelis Corneliszoon van Haarlem, *Adam et Ève au paradis terrestre* [*Adam and Eve in the Earthly Paradise*], 1625. Musée des Beaux-Arts de Quimper, France. Image available from :

<https://www.mbaq.fr/en/our-collections/the-flemish-and-dutch-paintings/adam-et-eve-au-paradis-terrestre-645.html>

17, Guido Reni, *Adam et Ève au Paradis* [*Adam and Eve in Paradise*], ca. 1620. Musée des Beaux-Arts de Dijon, France.

Image available from: <https://musees.dijon.fr/artworks/adam-et-eve-au-paradis/>

18, Heinrich Aldegrever, *The Fall of Mankind*, 1541 (plate 2 of the series “The Power of Death/ Allegory of Original Sin and Death”). After Hans Holbein the Younger. The British Museum, London. Image available from:

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19, Unknown British artist, *Display dish with the Temptation of Adam and Eve*, ca. 1650. The Met, OA. Image available from:

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<https://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O11566/the-temptation-of-adam-and-dish-pickleherring-pottery/>

1

a

b

Umbilical peduncle

2

3

4

Figure 15. A Subtle Umbilical Motif.

Perhaps Images 2 and 3 are the only ones I have ever seen where Eve has already eaten part of the apple. In both Images 2 and 4, Adam takes the apple directly from the serpent, much like the embryo, who receives nourishment directly through the umbilical cord from food already ingested by the pregnant mother. In Image 3, Adam's penis is already erect, even though he has not yet eaten the apple. The mere act of touching the fruit is enough to provoke arousal. This subtly reveals that the true consumer of the apple is, in fact, the son — while the depicted figure of the man represents the father, whose desire is ignited simply by touching, or perhaps merely beholding, the woman's rounded forms.

Perhaps Image 4 is the depiction of original sin that most clearly reveals the serpent not as a mere seducer, but as a tangible link connecting Adam/Cain to both Eve and the apple. Here, "Adam" does not even wait for Eve to take the apple from the serpent's mouth before being seduced by it; instead, he reaches for the fruit himself — either from Eve or directly from the serpent — while the woman is still grasping it, as if competing with her for

the serpent's offering. This suggests that Eve-serpent is not seducing Adam, but rather functioning as a physical conduit between him and the apple: as Adam reaches forward, his hand nearly touches both Eve's hand and the serpent's mouth, forming a chain of contact that subtly reveals the serpent's deeper identity — as an umbilical cord. Adam's apparent competition with Eve, who has already begun to eat, evokes the child's "rivalry" with the mother for the food she consumes — food that nourishes the child through the umbilical link. Note also that, in Image 4, the apple's stem cavity is clearly oriented toward the viewer — a rare motif in depictions of the Fall — with the peduncle still attached.

Images:

1, One of the first collages I created to illustrate my theory, before delving more profoundly into the visual codes of original sin.

1.a, Albrecht Dürer, *Adam and Eve*, 1504. The Met, OA.

1.b, *The umbilical region, the cord, and the placenta at term. (About half natural size).* Figure 32 on page 29 of *Embryology, Anatomy, and Diseases of the Umbilicus, Together with Diseases of the Urachus* written by Thomas Stephen Cullen,

illustrated by Max Brödel: Philadelphia and London, W. B. Saunders Company, 1916.

1.c, *An apple borne on the tree*. Image by Melanie from Pixabay.

2, Heinrich Aldegrever, *The Temptation by the Snake*, 1540. NGA, OA.

3, Follower of Hans Schilling, from the Workshop of Diebold Lauber, *The Garden of Eden and Adam and Eve Eating the Forbidden Fruit*, 1469. Illumination on folio 1v of Rudolf von Ems, *Barlaam und Josaphat [Barlaam and Josaphat]*. Ms. Ludwig XV 9, fol. 1v. The J. Paul Getty Museum, Getty Centre, Los Angeles. Getty, Open.

4, Sebald Beham, *Adam and Eve*, 1543. State two (a) of five states. After Barthel Beham. The Met, OA.

Figure 16. The Third “Apple”: A Symbol of Cain.

With one exception (Image 14), the only depictions of original sin I know in which Adam holds the apple by its peduncle, or its little branch – that is, the umbilical cord – are by Lucas van Leyden: Images 4 and 6, though in Images 6 and 11 – as in Images 2, 9, and Figures 2.1 (p. 53) and 12.3 (p. 89) – the serpent also holds it by the cord, and Eve does so as in Images 1, 3 (left hand), 9, and Figure 2.1. Strikingly, van Leyden – in Image 6 and Figure 13.12 (p. 103) – along with numerous other artists who depicted the same biblical scene (Figures 8.1, 12.3, 12.7, 12.10, 13.2, 13.8, 13.21, 14.11, 16.1, 16.3, 16.7, 16.8 and 16.9) – chose to represent not two apples, as tradition suggests, but three or even four, held between the three protagonists – and with different sizes.

The Adam who holds the apple by its slender branch – its cord – is, in truth, less the primordial man than his son, Cain. If he is indeed Adam, he is taking – or rather, seeing – the apple of seduction: that is, Eve’s belly, where Cain’s umbilical cord shall later form; and offering her with his penis the fullness of that belly, where the future Cain shall soon take root. This explains why

depictions of original sin often show more than two apples: the supernumerary fruits signify the offspring of the first couple.

In Image 8, the apple Eve reserves for herself seems bigger than the other two, because it represents the gravid belly. This reading is further clarified in Image 4: Adam's face, suffused with a seductive expression, turns toward Eve, while the serpent gazes intently at him, as if poised to offer him the second apple it holds in its mouth. The interplay between Adam's posture above Eve and her hesitant expression suggests not that she is handing him the apple, but rather receiving it from him. This is also evident in Figure 12.9 (p. 89), where Adam, having received (or seen) the apple-belly from Eve, now takes the apple from the serpent-penis to offer it to her — or rather places his share of Cain's "apple" into the mouth of the serpent-cord. Yet the very fact that Adam touches the apple's slender stem — its symbolic cord — suggests that he represents Cain: the embryo receiving from Eve's right hand his own embryonic apple — smaller, more delicate, and quietly set apart from the others in Image 6. Though the image remains ambiguous, it is essential to discern the presence of Cain within

depictions of Adam and Eve's sin, in order to disentangle, as far as possible, the intertwined figures of father and son.

Image 8 can scarcely be interpreted as a condensation of sequential moments in the act of sinning, as Eve merely holds a fruit in her right hand and does not appear to offer it to Adam — who, instead, seems to consume the fruit she places between the teeth of the serpent-umbilical cord.

In image 10, Eve also cradles a third, small apple near her belly — or rather, a fourth, for I have just noticed that, in addition to the apple in Adam's left hand, the one in Eve's right, and the one she is offering to Adam, there is yet another lodged in the serpent's mouth. In image 12, the apple-body the serpent reserves for the embryo is noticeably smaller than the seductive apple-belly Eve offers to Adam or he offers to her as pregnant belly. She may also be read as the daughter receiving her apple-body from father and mother — through phallus and umbilical cord — though my focus here remains on Eve as the mother of Cain.

In Image 1, Adam places his hand on a third apple (framed in red), depicted between him and Eve, who already holds one in

her left hand while offering another with her right. In Image 9, Eve takes from the serpent two apples intended for Adam, while already holding two: one for herself, one for Adam, one for their or his son, and one for their or her daughter? See also Image 13, in which Eve extends a branch bearing multiple fruits toward Adam, rather than offering a single apple. This gesture suggests not only the offering of a sexualised fruit – her body – to her husband, but also the bestowal of apple-bodies to her children; it further evokes a broader notion of generative transmission (Figure 20.3, p. 155).

Images 1, 2 and 3 are the only depictions of original sin I know in which the apple Eve offers to Adam is positioned before his torso. In Image 1, the “navel” of the apple – distinguished by the presence of a leaf on its side – is oriented toward Adam’s body, as though functioning as a mirror image of his own navel. In Image 2, the apple’s stem-cavity is turned toward the viewer, as if inviting comparison between the cavity and a navel. Unlike the cavity visible in Image 1, that of Adam’s apple in Image 3 can scarcely be taken for a blossom end, owing both to its considerable size and

to the surrounding curvature, which more closely resembles that of a stem-cavity. This stem-cavity is turned toward the viewer, more distinctly than in Image 2, and without a stem, as though inviting a visual analogy with the severed navel.

In both Images 1 and 3, a peculiar black dot resembling a second navel is visible on a third apple placed between Adam and Eve. This third apple appears malleable, slightly compressed between the first man's thumb and index finger; it represents Cain, and its pliability evoke the umbilical cord of the "apple"-Cain.

In Image 5, Adam points with his index finger to an apple lying on the ground. Might this serve as a clear symbol of the notion that, in the narrative of the Fall brought about by means of an apple, Man himself is the apple that "fell" from the mother? In essence, the fallen Man is but a newborn, scarcely greater than that apple resting upon the earth.

Images:

1, Jan Saenredam, *Zondeval met vrouwelijke slang [The Fall of Man with a Female Serpent]*, 1597. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

2, Jan Saenredam, *Zondeval [The Fall of man]*, 1605.

Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

3, Christoffel van Sichem, *Zondeval met vrouwelijke slang [The Fall of Man with a Female Serpent]*, ca. 1646, detail.

Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

4, Lucas van Leyden, *Sin of Adam and Eve*, 1529. The Met, OA.

5, Illustration from Willem van Branteghem, *Pomarium mysticum tum novorum tum veterum fructuum, animae Christianae*, p. 10. Antwerp: Willem Vorsterman, 1535.

Accessible via Google books: [Pomarium mysticum - Google Books](#)

6, Lucas van Leyden, *The Fall of Man*, ca. 1517. The Met, OA.

7, Unknown sculptor, *Sündenfall [The Fall of Man]*, third scene on the left wing of Bishop Bernward's Doors, 1015. St Mary's Cathedral, Hildesheim, Germany. Photograph by Dr Franz Stœdtner, reproduced in Franz Dibelius, *Die Bernwardstür zu Hildesheim [The Bernward Doors in Hildesheim]*, p. 160 (Tafel 4). Strasbourg: Heitz & Mündel, 1907. Available from:

https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_p4gZAAAAYAAJ/page/n167/mode/2up?view=theater

8, Unknown artist, depiction of the Fall on a 15th-century misericord at Worcester Cathedral, England. Photo © Carolyn Whitson, Ph.D. 2023. Reproduced with kind permission.

www.pilgrimtothepast.com

9, Jacob Jordaens, *The Fall of Man*, 17th century, detail. Museum of Fine Arts, Budapest. PDI from Wikipedia, with permission from the Web Gallery of Art.

10, Lucas van Leyden, *The Fall of Man*, 1519. The British Museum, London. Available from:

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/P_1845-0809-925

11, Lucas van Leyden, *Fall of Man*, 1529. The Met, OA.

12, Albrecht Altdorfer, *The Fall of Man* (from “The Fall and Salvation of Mankind Through the Life and Passion of Christ” series), ca. 1513. The Met, OA.

13, Unknown artist, *Adam and Eve*. Illumination on folio 41v of the *Lancelot-Grail Cycle* (Vulgate Cycle), ca. 1316. British Library, London. Add. MS 10294. Available from:

<https://www.bridgemanimages.com/en/noworkknown/adam-and-eve/nomedium/asset/3279199?offline=1>

14, Michel Wolgemut, *Creation of Eve and Original Sin*, 1491. Book illustration from Stephan Fridolin, *Schatzbehälter der wahren Reichtümer des Heils* [*Treasury of the true riches of salvation*]. Nuremberg: Anton Koberger, 1491. The British Museum, London. Available from:

https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/object/P_A-9-1-91?selectedImageId=1613673690

Figure 17. No sin, no scar: no apple, no navel.

In Image 1, Eve – who here represents the daughter – appears to lack a severed navel as she reaches for the apple, that is, while still attached to the tree by the umbilical cord, but suddenly acquires one as she begins to eat it. In Image 2, the genitals of Adam and Eve are concealed even before the transgression. As the Cleveland Museum of Art notes, this mosaic depicts “two moments in the biblical narrative”: the act of sin and the ensuing realisation of nakedness (Genesis 3:7). Such condensation – reminiscent of

dream logic — is common in visual renderings of the Fall. Yet here, the leaf that conceals Adam’s genitals also covers his navel at the very moment he receives the apple from Eve. This concealment seems to reject any symbolic connection between the Fall and birth (of Cain). And yet, given the dream-like fusion of narrative layers, it may also imply that Adam/Cain has not yet acquired a navel — that the apple has not been consumed, and the umbilical cord remains uncut. Similarly, in the upper-left scene of Image 3 — whose lower-right scene features Adam’s navel concealed by the petiole of the leaf that also veils his genitals, as if to affirm that the shameful punishment of Original Sin is the severing of the umbilical cord — Adam/Cain appears to lack a navel as he is “giving birth” to Eve; that is, precisely as the woman is giving birth to him: a Freudian reversal of roles.

Images:

1, Unknown artist, *The Temptation and Fall*, ca. 830–840. Illumination on folio 5v of *The Moutier-Grandval Bible*. From the British Library Collection: Add. MS 10546. Reproduced with kind permission.

2, Unknown artist, *Adam and Eve*, late 5th-early 6th century CE. Fragment of a floor mosaic from an early Byzantine church in Northern Syria. The Cleveland Museum of Art. Image made available by the Museum under a Creative Commons Zero (CC0) designation as part of their Open Access programme, abbreviated below as CMA, OA. Source material available from:

<https://www.clevelandart.org/art/1969.115>

3, Unidentified German artist, *Scenes from the Book of Genesis: the Creation of Eve, the Marriage of Adam and Eve, the Temptation, and the Expulsion*, mid-13th century. Courtesy of the Barnes Foundation, Merion and Philadelphia, Pennsylvania; abbreviated thereafter as “Barnes”.

Figure 18. Origin in Hair and Navel.

I know of several drawings where the navel, quite astonishingly, appears through a garment whose fabric is too thick to allow it. See, for instance, the navel of Eve and that of the cherub chasing

Adam and Eve out of the Garden in Image 1. Note also, in Image 3, the navel of God expelling Adam and Eve from Paradise – which is more faithful to the text than images depicting their expulsion by a cherub, and, as noted by a University of Chicago student (*Witnessing Medieval Evil*, 2020), establishes a more direct connection to God – visible through His clothing, and Adam’s likewise discernible beneath the fabric in the right-hand scene of the composition.

The navel is linked to the hair whorl. See the navel-shaped hole on the apex of Adam’s head in Image 1. Is this merely a hair whorl? Note how the vertex of the scalp, visible through the hair, lacks the clarity of Adam’s skin tone and appears darker, making this area resemble an umbilicus on an apple-like head. A comparable navel-like mark appears in Image 2, where the dark, rounded form atop the head of the father – who is examining the stars with an astrologer at the birth of his child – more closely evokes the stem-cavity of an apple than the top of a beanie.

While Adam’s navel is plainly visible – even through the fabric of his clothing, and perhaps even through the tree stem in

the left-hand scene (see the encircled detail) — Eve’s is nowhere to be seen in this depiction. Her surprisingly *veiled hair*, however, seems to symbolically stand in for the umbilical cord, as though the sign of origin had been transposed.

The interpretation of hair as a symbol of the umbilical cord aligns with the iconography of Medusa (Image 4), whose hair, composed of serpents, evokes a primal connection to origin and identity. A corresponding motif appears in Image 5, where Eve’s hair, the serpent itself, and the serpent’s own hair dissolve into near indistinction; another emerges on the recto of the very folio whose verso bears Image 3, where a delicate lock of Eve’s hair descends with deliberate precision to veil her navel.

Images:

1, Jan Saenredam, *Expulsion from Paradise*, 1604. Rijksmuseum, Amsterdam.

2, Jost Amman, *The Birth Chamber*. Illustration on folio 3r of *De Conceptu Et Generatione Hominis* written by Jacob Rueff: Frankfurt am Main, Sigmund Feyerabend, 1587. Internet Archive.

Available from:

https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_EpPvNIFjigC/page/n17/mode/2up?view=theater

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3, Anonymous English artist, *Expulsion from the Garden of Eden - Adam and Eve* labouring. Illumination on folio 7v of an Old English Hexateuch, 2nd quarter of 11th century. From the British Library Collection: Cotton MS Claudius B IV. The recto is available from:

<https://gorbutovich.livejournal.com/103775.html>

4, Unknown artist/maker, *Antefix depicting the head of Medusa*, 4th century BCE. The Met, OA.

5, John Roddam Spencer Stanhope, *The Temptation of Eve*, 1887. Private collection, USA. PDI from Wikimedia Commons.

Figure 19. Fruit versus Tree.

The embryo recalls a fruit; as it grows, it increasingly assumes the semblance of a tree. Yet the human body, even unto death, preserves its likeness to the apple, by virtue of the resemblance between the apple's stem-cavity and the navel.

Images:

1, Diagrammatic sketches from Figure 9 on page 45 of *Anatomy of the Human Body* by Henry Gray, 1858. Twentieth edition: Philadelphia and New York, Lea & Febiger, 1918. “First stages of segmentation of a mammalian ovum. Semidiagrammatic. (From a drawing by Allen Thomson.) z.p. Zona striata. p.gl. Polar bodies. a. Two-cell stage. b. Four-cell stage. c. Eight-cell stage.” d. Morula stage.

2, Figure 32 on page 59 of Gray, 1858. “Section through ovum imbedded in the uterine decidua. Semidiagrammatic. (After Peters.) *am.* Amniotic cavity. *b.c.* Blood-clot. *b.s.* Body-stalk. *ect.* Embryonic ectoderm. *ent.* Entoderm. *mes.* Mesoderm. *m.v.* Maternal vessels. *tr.* Trophoblast. *u.e.* Uterine epithelium. *u.g.* Uterine glands, *y.s.* Yolk-sac.”

3, Digram from Figure 70 on page 81 of *A Laboratory Manual and Text-Book of Embryology* by Charles William Prentiss: Philadelphia and London, W. B. Saunders Company, 1915. One of “Four diagrams showing hypothetical stages of early human embryos (based on figures of Robinson and Minot)”.

4, Figure 39 on page 64 of Gray, 1858, detail. Scheme of placental circulation.

5, Figure 34 on page 61 of Gray, 1858. “Sectional plan of the gravid uterus in the third and fourth month. (Modified from Wagner.)”

6, Figure 30 on page 57 of Gray, 1858. “Foetus of about eight weeks, enclosed in the amnion. Magnified a little over two diameters. (Drawn from stereoscopic photographs lent by Prof. A. Thomson, Oxford.)”

7, Figure 23 on page 54 of Gray, 1858. “Human embryo from thirty-one to thirty-four days. (His.)”

8, Drawing from Figure 86 on page 95 of Prentiss, 1915. Embryo “of the second month from His’ Normentafel (Keibel and Elze)”.

9 and 11, Figures 2 and 1 (cropped) from Akinmoladun J, Lawal T, Bello O. “Pattern of prenatal ultrasound diagnosed anterior abdominal wall defects at the University College Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria: A pictorial essay”. *West Afr J Radiol* 2019;26:43-9.

https://doi.org/10.4103/wajr.wajr_7_18 Image 9: “Ultrasound of a foetus at 10 weeks’ gestation showing physiological herniation of midgut (arrow)”. Image 11: “Transverse scan of the fetal abdomen

at 20 weeks showing normal insertion of the umbilical cord (arrow)". *West African Journal of Radiology* © 2018. Published by Wolters Kluwer - Medknow and distributed under the CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 licence. Images reproduced under the same licence.

<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>

10 and 12, Three-dimensional ultrasound images in surface mode of foetuses at 10 and 12 weeks of gestation, respectively. From Figures 12.5 and 12.9 in "The Fetal Gastrointestinal System" [Internet; cited 22 June 2025]. Available from:

<https://radiologykey.com/the-fetal-gastrointestinal-system/>

At 10 weeks, a physiologic midgut herniation is visible "as a bulge at the site of cord insertion into the abdomen (*arrow*)"; by 12 weeks, the anatomy is consistent with "the normal insertion of the umbilical cord in the abdomen" (*arrow*).

Images reproduced with kind permission of Radiology Key.

13, Albrecht Dürer, *Madonna and Child*, ca. 1496-1499. NGA, OA.

14, Willem Vrelant, *Adam and Eve Eating the Forbidden Fruit* (leaf from a Book of Hours, *Arenberg Hours*, early 1460s, fol. 137). Getty, Open.

15, Jost Amman, *Fall of Man*. Illustration on page 1 of *De Conceptu Et Generatione Hominis* by Jacob Rueff: Frankfurt am Main, Sigmund Feyerabend, 1587. Digitized by Internet Archive.

Available from:

https://archive.org/details/bub_gb_EpPvNIFjtgC/page/n3/mode/2up?view=theater

Figure 20. Jesus as Adam/Cain: The First Birth and Its Redemption.

The early Fathers of the Church had already discerned in Jesus a new Adam, and in Mary, his mother, a new Eve (cf. *supra*, p. 24) – an insight that lends further weight to my interpretation, according to which the Adam of the Fall narrative is condensed with the first-born, and indeed all those born of Eve. The artists, in turn, did not fail to convey this idea. Some even went so far as to depict Anne offering the apple to Jesus. In Images 1 and 2, it is Mary who presents the apple to Jesus (see also Image 6, echoing Luke 1.42). In Image 1, Jesus holds a string of prayer beads, their cord grazing his navel. Yet before passing the “apple” to her son, Mary herself has received her own “apple” from Anne, her mother. In this sense, Mary is but the final bead in the chain through which the apple was transmitted from Eve and Adam to Jesus (Image 3). Unlike that of Mary Magdalene, Mary’s apple is not sexualised. Yet through her faith and her sublimated love for Jesus, God cleanses Magdalene’s sin with a ray of light – or a breath of wind – emerging from His navel (Image 4).

Images:

1, Circle of Gerard David, *Virgin and Child*, Early 16th century.

Barnes.

2, Unidentified Upper Rhenish artist, *Madonna and Child*, Last quarter of 15th century. Barnes.

3, Lucas van Leyden, *The Virgin and Saint Anna*, 1516. NGA, OA.

4, Lucas van Leyden, *Saint Mary Magdalene in the Desert*, ca. 1508. NGA, OA.

5, Circle of Michel Erhart, *Christ Child with an Apple*, ca. 1470-80. The Met, OA.

6, Fairfield Porter, *Wild Apples*, 1969. Available from:

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/486278>

Figure 21. A Visual Revelation.

I had previously noted that Figures 16.1, 2 and 3 (p. 134) were the only depictions of original sin I knew in which the apple offered by Eve is positioned before Adam's torso. This, however, was before I encountered this astonishing illustration from a Middle English poem describing the soul's journey towards divine love and mystic communion with God. In this rendering of the Fall of Man – where Adam and Eve, even more markedly than in Figure 13.13 (p. 103), stand in visible estrangement – Adam holds the apple not merely before his torso, but with uncanny precision before his navel, as if to suggest that the fruit symbolically corresponds to this part of his body.

Image:

Francis Barlow, *The Fall of Man*. Illustration facing page 24 of *Theophila, or Loves Sacrifice* written by Edward Benlowes: London, Henry Seile and Humphrey Moseley, 1652. Digitized by Internet Archive. [Internet; cited 20 June 2025]. Available from:

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1641-1700_theophila-or-loves-sacr_benlowes-edward_1652/page/n77/mode/2up?view=theater.

A contrast-faithful photograph from a copy of *Theophila*, gifted by St John's College Library to the University of Minnesota, is available from:

<https://manifold.umn.edu/projects/cut-copy-paste/resource/r081>

Disclosure Statement

The author declares no competing interests.

On the Author's Identity

I have chosen to publish this work under the pen name Jonas Noble – not to conceal my identity, but to enable my audience – particularly in the West – to approach my ideas free from cultural and biographical prejudice, with the rigour and openness they merit.

Nabil Younis is my real name. Born into the Greek Orthodox tradition in Lebanon, I am neither conventionally religious nor atheist – and beyond doubt not purely Christian. The very Science, the very Psychoanalysis, prevent me from being purely Christian – yet so too do the Christian sufferings I endured, especially at the hands of my own father, after my parents' "adultery"... pardon, their *disunion*... when I was six... By revealing my identity here, I seek to honour both the universality of inquiry and the uniqueness of my own contribution.

After all, my pen name is a literal English rendering of my real one. Over the years, I have published several books in the French language – most notably *L'Œdipe anti-freudien* [*The Anti-Freudian Oedipus*] – under the name Eugène Jonas, itself a direct French translation of my official name. My definitive pen name, however, adopts the word “Noble”, which more faithfully reflects my given name, Nabil – though with given name and patronym reversed. This inversion was guided by the greater familiarity of *Jonas* as a first name in the West, as well as by the natural reversal that occurs in moving from Arabic, written right to left, to English, written left to right. The choice was also phonetically deliberate: *Jonas Noble* sounds more harmonious than *Noble Jonas*.

In my name, the patronym *Jonas* – etymologically rooted in the “dove”, a timeless emblem of peace – resonates with my late mother’s Arabic given name, *Salam*, which means “peace”. In many respects, Salam stood as both mother and *pater* to me; without that resonance between her name and *Younes* – as written on my Lebanese passport, or Younis, as I prefer to render it in closer fidelity to its Arabic pronunciation – I would have accepted

the patronym of my pseudo-father only with reluctance — let alone allowed it to enter public recognition — despite my deep respect for the name itself and its religious significance.

The central thesis of the present work originated in September 2003, when I first began deciphering the symbolic structure of the narrative of the Fall. The discovery of the latent meaning of the apple was made on 3 October 2003. An early version of my theory appeared, not until November 2012, under my real name, in a French book entitled *Psychanalyse de la Bible* [*Psychoanalysis of the Bible*], now withdrawn from circulation. What I present here, twenty-two years after the decisive discovery, is a seasoned, considerably refined elaboration of the ideas first articulated in that edition — signed this time not with a patronym shadowed by misogyny, but by a Jonas who bears, with nobility, the honesty of Salam.

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³ The majority of the books in the author’s library are in French; many of the translations cited here were thankfully accessed through Internet Archive: www.internetarchive.org.

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